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**REPORT ON DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION INCLUDING,
STANDARDIZATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES (FINAL)**

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Abstract	This report summarizes the final outcomes of the "All Data 4 Green Deal" (AD4GD) project, detailing its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities aimed at establishing a FAIR and standards-based Green Deal Data Space (GDSS)
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Program Interface
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GWF	Geospatial World Forum
IDSA	International Data Space Association
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SDO	Standards Development Organizations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The AD4GD project successfully established foundational frameworks for the European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS), demonstrating how FAIR principles and open standards can enable interoperable environmental data sharing across water quality, biodiversity, and air pollution domains. The following summary highlights the project's key achievements.

Communication and Outreach Success:

The project's communication strategy significantly exceeded expectations:

- **Website engagement:** 11,300 visits (target: 5,000)
- **Video content:** 51 explanatory videos produced (target: 5)
- **Workshop delivery:** 31 workshops organized (target: 10)
- **Social media reach:** 874 followers across platforms (target: 500)
- **Material distribution:** 2,783 digital and printed materials (target: 2,500)

Effective Knowledge Transfer:

AD4GD demonstrated strong commitment to capacity building and knowledge transfer:

- **Student support:** 6 PhD and 9 MSc students directly involved in project activities
- **Authority connection:** 12 targeted meetings with local and regional authorities
- **Standards reuse:** Successfully integrated diverse standards from OGC, FIWARE, W3C, and other bodies

Practical Implementations:

The project delivered three operational pilots demonstrating real-world applications:

- **Berlin Water Pilot:** Smart monitoring of 400+ urban lakes using IoT sensors and satellite data
- **Catalonia Biodiversity Pilot:** Habitat connectivity analysis using citizen science and remote sensing
- **Air Quality Pilot:** Low-cost sensor networks for urban air quality monitoring

Strategic Collaboration:

AD4GD fostered meaningful partnerships within the European research ecosystem:

- **Sister Projects:** Close collaboration with FAIRiCUBE, USAGE, and B-Cubed projects
- **EuroGEO Integration:** Established the Green Deal Data Space Action Group within EuroGEO
- **Joint Policy Brief:** Co-authored comprehensive policy recommendations with sister projects

Standardization:

AD4GD integrated 21 existing open standards into its information model, exceeding the target of 10. This standards-first approach ensured that AD4GD's technical developments aligned with existing international frameworks while contributing to their evolution.

The project also successfully contributed to major standardization bodies including:

- **OGC Standards:** CREAM was the main editor of OGC API - Tiles Part 1: Core, Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF Standard, and OGC API - Maps Part 1: Core
- **FIWARE Extensions:** Proposed water-related smart data models for urban lake monitoring
- **Privacy Standards:** Developed specialized Europrivacy criteria for Earth Observation data processing under GDPR

Sustainable Impact:

The project's exploitation strategy identified three Key Exploitable Results (KERs):

1. **Core Components:** Nine foundational technical elements enabling FAIR data interoperability

2. **Tools and Services:** User interface applications such as SplashBoard, BioConnect and the generic GDDS portal
3. **Validated Use Cases:** Real-world pilot implementations demonstrating scalability

Legacy and Future Impact:

AD4GD's contributions extend beyond its project timeline:

- **Open Access Resources:** All major outputs available through Zenodo, GitHub, and partner platforms
- **Technical Standards:** Contributions now embedded in international standards used by the global community
- **Policy Influence:** Joint policy brief providing actionable recommendations for GDDS development
- **Community Building:** Established networks and collaboration mechanisms continuing through EuroGEO
- **Future projects:** The coordinator is part of the SAGE project that is going to deploy the operational GDDS.

The project successfully balanced technical innovation with practical stakeholder needs, creating a robust foundation for the European Green Deal Data Space that prioritizes interoperability, citizen participation, and evidence-based environmental decision-making. Through its emphasis on open standards and collaborative development, AD4GD has positioned the European environmental data ecosystem for sustainable growth and impact.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 7.2 Report on dissemination and exploitation including, standardization and communication activities (final) presents an overview of the communication, dissemination, exploitation, and standardization efforts carried out in the AD4GD project, from its initiation to its completion. This report, based on the strategy outlined in *Deliverable 7.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Standardization and Communication Activities*¹, documents the development, execution, and effects of the outreach and engagement activities under Work Package 7 on Standardization, Outreach, and Exploitation, led by MI, and supported by CREAM, OGC, DT, and all project partners.

The goal of AD4GD has been to research how to develop the European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) as an open, FAIR, and standards-compliant center for data and services related to the priorities of the Green Deal, specifically looking at water quality, biodiversity, and air pollution. Since the start of the project, communication and dissemination have been an essential activity, aimed at sharing the AD4GD objectives and outcomes with a diverse range of stakeholders, while also engaging communities, promoting adoption, and establishing a foundation for sustainability and legacy.

This deliverable includes the entire range of communication, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation activities across the project lifecycle (see section 1.3) from the early foundational phase focused on identity-building and stakeholder-mapping, through the growth and maturity phases characterized by intensive dissemination and community-building, and to the closing and legacy phases oriented around sustainability, standardization engagement, and exploitation of results.

This deliverable presents quantitative metrics and qualitative insights to transparently document achievements, lessons learnt, and recommendations for future initiatives focused on interoperable, citizen-centric, and data-driven solutions for Europe's green transition.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this deliverable is to:

- Provide a final overview of all communication, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation activities carried out during the AD4GD project;
- Evaluate the implementation of the strategies defined in D7.1 and their alignment with the project's overarching objectives;
- Highlight key achievements, outcomes, and impacts resulting from these activities;
- Document lessons learned, and identify opportunities for continued engagement and exploitation of AD4GD results beyond the project's lifetime.

1.2 DELIVERABLE STRUCTURE

The deliverable is structured into 5 sections, as follows:

1. *Introduction*: provision of the context for the deliverable, including objectives and an overview of project phases.
2. *Communication activities*: a detailed view of the project's media outreach, newsletters, online presence, and stakeholder engagement initiatives and their outcomes.
3. *Dissemination activities*: a summary of scientific outputs, presentations, participation in events, and contributions to the broader research and policy landscape, as well as a review of liaisons with Standards Development Organizations (SDOs), contributions to standardization bodies, and the integration of standards within the project.
4. *Exploitation activities*: an overview of exploitation activities and key outcomes.

¹ [D7.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including Standardization and Communication Activities](#)

5. *Conclusion*: reflections on the success of the project's outreach and engagement efforts, along with strategic takeaways and lessons learned.

1.3 PROJECT PHASES

Figure 1 AD4GD Dissemination, exploitation, standardization, and communication roadmap, as defined in D7.1

As illustrated in Figure 1, a four-phase roadmap was developed to facilitate the effective execution of communication, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation efforts.

1.3.1 PHASE 1 – LAUNCH (M01–M08)

This launch phase focused on establishing the project's identity and setting the stage for future outreach. Key achievements included:

- Development of the AD4GD branding, including the logo, visual assets, and templates;
- Launch of the project website and social media channels;
- Definition and refining of target audiences and stakeholder segments;
- Initial outreach to Sister Projects and alignment with EU Green Deal priorities.

1.3.2 PHASE 2 – GROWTH (M09–M24)

The growth phase emphasized expansion, visibility, and engagement. It marked a shift from planning to active implementation, with highlights such as:

- Delivery of newsletters, flyers, and presentations to the target audience and stakeholder segments;
- Participation in conferences, workshops, and community events;
- Development of early demonstrators and communication of pilot activities;
- Launch of partner interviews and storytelling formats to engage non-specialist audiences.

1.3.3 PHASE 3 – CLOSING (M24–M36)

As the project matured, the closing phase focused on communicating final results and preparing for sustainability. Key outcomes included:

- Finalization and dissemination of Key Exploitable Results (KERs);
- Strategic alignment of partner exploitation plans;
- Expanded liaison with Standards Development Organizations (SDOs);
- Increased focus on impactful publications and policy engagement.

1.3.4 PHASE 4 – LEGACY (POST-M36)

Although outside the contractual reporting period, this phase is already being prepared to ensure continuity and impact. Planned legacy actions include:

- Long-term hosting and maintenance of the project website;
- Continued engagement with stakeholders through social media and community groups;
- Promotion of project outputs and standards via partner networks and EU platforms;
- Identification of opportunities for scale-up or spin-off of key results.

2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Communication activities have been important to the AD4GD project's strategy to inform, engage, and establish a network of stakeholders across several domains and regions. These activities were executed during the project's duration and customized for several target groups, including academics, researchers, policymakers, citizens, and industry stakeholders.

The main goal of communication within AD4GD was not only to raise awareness about the project, but to create a lasting visibility and impact of the project outcomes. The following sections provide a detailed summary of the tools, platforms, and materials created and distributed, as well as the outreach and engagement results.

2.1 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were originally defined in Deliverable 7.1 as benchmarks to guide and assess the effectiveness of the project's communication efforts:

Indicator	Impact	Source
Visits to AD4GD website	≥ 5000	Visitor counter
Explanatory videos	≥ 5	Videos generated and uploaded
Organized workshops, including demonstration workshops	≥ 10	Internal and external workshops
Demonstration workshops, forums / total participants	4 / ≥ 250	External demonstration workshops/forums / participants in total to all workshops/forums
Articles in online blogs and newspapers	≥ 200	Number of articles/blogs generated by partners and published on the AD4GD website and externally
Distributed printed/digital material	≥ 2500	Number of handed out printed material/number of downloads-sent material
E-newsletter recipients	≥ 500	Mailing and subscriber list record
Followers/subscribers on social media	≥ 500	Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube subscriber/follower number
Organized open events	≥ 5	Partners' reports on communication activities

Table 1 Communication activities KPIs

2.2 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Stakeholder engagement has been a fundamental component of AD4GD's outreach strategy. Target groups were defined early on (including civil society and citizens, policymakers & local and regional authorities, decision makers, researcher communities, European projects, and developers at industry/commercial organizations) and engagement strategies were adapted accordingly.

2.2.1 TARGET GROUPS

D7.1 has already outlined the relationship between the communication activities and the segmented target groups (see Table 2 Communication strategy matrix) and indicated the measures through which impact was expected to be generated:

Who	What	How
Civil society and citizens (SEG1)	Less technical language so that a non-specialist audience can easily understand the goals and means of the project	Website, social media, mass media, e-newsletter, demonstrations
Policy makers, local and regional authorities (SEG2)	Project goals as well as successful or exemplary activities and results	Website, e-newsletter, networking, round table with policy maker, policy briefs, demonstrations
Decision makers, including industrial stakeholders, data providers and developers, and the innovation community (SEG3)	Focus on the technology enablers, measured impacts, potential economic exploitation and societal benefits	Website, e-newsletter, networking, scientific publications, round table with decision makers, policy briefs, demonstrations
Research communities (SEG4)	Detailed scientific and technical results	Website, e-newsletter, social media, networking, scientific publications, briefings, demonstrations, collaboration with projects and networks, invitation to seminars and talks, conferences and events attendance, participation and organization of workshops and PhD schools
European projects (SEG5)	Detailed scientific and technical results	Website, e-newsletter, social media, networking, publications, demonstrations, participation in other projects events, Project Boards
Developers at industry/commercial organizations (SEG6)	Implementation guidelines and best practices in the form of coding sprints	Website, e-newsletter, social media, networking, publications, demonstrations

Table 2 Target group segments and means of information sharing

The following sections will provide further information on how these objectives were reached and how the partners generated impact by targeting the specific segments.

2.2.2 SISTER PROJECTS

AD4GD established connection with the three Sister Projects, namely:

- F.A.I.R. information cube (FAIRiCUBE)
- Urban Data Spaces for Green dEal (USAGE)
- Biodiversity Building Blocks for policy (B3)

This connection spanned through bilateral meetings, joint participation in events, joint publications, as well as jointly organized workshops and meetings. Additionally, a monthly communication-focused meeting was set up between the 4 projects where the communication work package and task leaders gathered to discuss impact-generation and set out to ensure mutual social media promotion.

Additionally, with various extents, AD4GD has also engaged with other relevant projects working in related domains, including:

- Open-Earth-Monitor (OEMC)

- Digital Twin of the Ocean (ILIAD)
- The Data Space for a Sustainable Green Europe (SAGE)
- The GREAT Project – Green Deal Data Space (GREAT)

The list of joint activities includes:

- EuroGEO Workshop 2022
- Iliad Webinar 'Introduction to data spaces'
- OEMC Science Webinar - Tired of data tables full of data that I have no idea what it means? Use Sensor Things API
- Species Occurrence Cubes Workshop
- EuroGEO workshop 2023
- Open-Earth-Monitor Global Workshop 2023
- EC-ESA JOINT EARTH SYSTEM SCIENCE INITIATIVE Science for a Green and Sustainable Society
- INSPIRE Conference 2023
- Iliad Webinar Series: Data lakes and data spaces - Towards best practices
- Environmental and climate data in an evolving EU data policy landscape
- B3 Hackathon
- EuroGEO Workshop 2024
- Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space in EuroGEO

These joint efforts contributed to a cohesive voice around the Green Deal Data Space, increasing the visibility of the projects and their shared objectives, as well as harmonizing communication & dissemination across the broader research ecosystem.

2.2.3 EUROGEO GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE ACTION GROUP

A notable milestone was the creation of a dedicated EuroGEO Green Deal Data Space Action Group², initiated during EuroGEO 2022 with AD4GD participation and led by CREAM. This group became a coordination point among projects contributing to the Green Deal Data Space and its alignment with the EuroGEO and GEOSS frameworks. This Action Group now functions as a long-term coordination mechanism supporting the convergence of data space development across environmental domains. Through this initiative, AD4GD contributed directly to shaping the narrative and priorities around federated data infrastructures within EuroGEO and GEOSS. The long-term value of this collaborative initiative lies in its continued relevance beyond the duration of AD4GD. Embedded within the broader EuroGEO framework and supported by ongoing projects such as SAGE, the Action Group is well positioned to sustain coordination efforts and guide the evolution of data spaces for environmental applications.

A dedicated website for the EuroGEO Action Group was created and has been managed since by CREAM. It showcases the participating initiatives, provides a description for the Green Deal Data Space, and disseminates reports and blogs that are then cross communicated by the partners on their websites, social media platforms, and shared through their newsletters.

As part of its ongoing coordination role within the EuroGEO Action Group on Data Spaces, AD4GD also co-organized the event "*Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space in EuroGEO*", taking place in 24-25 June 2025 in Vienna, Austria parallel to the ESA Living Planet Symposium. This event brought together key actors across Sister Projects, European data initiatives, and policy stakeholders to further align data space developments with the goals of the European Green Deal. Detailed description of the event is available under Section 3.3.

2.3 VISUAL IDENTITY

² [EuroGEO Action Group on Data Spaces website](#)

The project visual identity was established early and has been consistently applied across all communication and dissemination materials. It was proposed by the CREAM communication area. As shown in D7.1, this identity includes the project logo, color palette, typography, templates, and graphical guidelines, designed to ensure recognizability, clarity, and alignment with EU visual communication standards.

The visual identity has been integrated into all external materials including:

- The AD4GD website
- Social media assets
- Flyers, newsletters, and roll-ups
- Project deliverables and presentation templates
- Event presentations and posters

All assets are openly available for download via the official AD4GD resources page³, allowing partners and collaborators to maintain visual consistency in their own outreach activities.

Additionally, posters were designed for major conferences and workshops followed the established visual identity. They aimed to present complex concepts such as semantic interoperability, FAIR data, and pilot case studies in an accessible, visually engaging format. Some examples include:

³ [AD4GD resources page](#)

Figure 2 EC-ESA Joint Earth System Science Initiative poster

Figure 3 GEO Week 2023 Ministerial Summit poster

2.4 AD4GD WEBSITE

The project website has served as the primary public-facing channel for communicating AD4GD’s objectives, progress, and outputs. Originally launched early in the project, the website has undergone a significant visual and structural redesign to improve usability, branding consistency, and content accessibility.

As described in D7.1, the original website was structured to provide an introduction to the project, information about its pilots, work packages, and consortium members, as well as access to news items and public deliverables. Visual consistency was ensured through the integration of the AD4GD branding and imagery, including homepage illustrations, icon sets, and pilot visuals.

In the reporting period, the website was significantly redesigned to improve readability, responsiveness, and content hierarchy, as well as the visual appeal. Key updates include:

- A restructured homepage⁴ with clearer messaging and thematic sections (project vision, pilots, FAIR principles).

⁴ [AD4GD home page](#)

- New or expanded sections, such as:
 - Green Deal Data Space⁵: presenting AD4GD's role and connections to the broader data space ecosystem.
 - Components⁶: homepage for accessing the 9 AD4GD key components and associated description and materials.
 - Resources⁷: now a centralized location for posters, visual identity materials, and public tools.
 - News⁸: showcasing the latest news about the project activities.
 - Upcoming and past events⁹: listing all upcoming and past events with AD4GD presence.
- The Pilots¹⁰ section was redesigned for deeper detail, interactive visual content, and easier navigation.
- Overall alignment with the visual identity and accessibility improvements (e.g., responsive design, improved contrast, simplified navigation).
- Addition of direct links to the newsletter subscription and the EuroGEO website.
- Removal of login and registration buttons to limit access to partners, prevent unnecessary sign-up attempts, and improve user experience.

What is the Green Deal **Data Space**?

The **Green Deal Data Space (GDSS)** is one of the common European data spaces envisioned by the European Commission to integrate enormous amounts of cross-sectorial data in support of the priority actions of the **European Green Deal** in terms of biodiversity, zero pollution, circular economy, climate change, forestal services, smart mobility and environmental compliance.

[Learn more](#)

Figure 4 AD4GD Home page and navigation

⁵ [What is the Green Deal Data Space?](#)

⁶ [Components page](#)

⁷ [Resources page](#)

⁸ [News page](#)

⁹ [Events page](#)

¹⁰ [Pilots main page](#)

Solutions aligned with the European Green Deal

AD4GD demonstrates how the developed building blocks could play a key role in shaping the future European Green Deal Data Space through three pilot cases focused on the European Green Deal priorities.

Biodiversity

Habitat connectivity affects the distribution of species within ecosystems. It is a key biodiversity indicator and, therefore, a cornerstone in European restoration policies. This pilot aims to monitor historical connectivity indices in Catalonia using data coming from remote sensing maps, species occurrence observations and sensor data to enhance regional and local actions.

[Learn more](#)

Air Quality

Poor urban air quality causes serious health issues across Europe. This pilot employs low-cost IoT sensors to enhance accurate and localized air pollution forecasting while involving citizen communities. The goal is to provide detailed local air quality insights that support informed health decisions and help to establish replicable models for urban air quality enhancement.

[Learn more](#)

Water

Berlin's small lakes are ecological hotspots at risk due to various climate and urban stressors. These lakes also suffer from a lack of information on their condition. This pilot project aims to develop indicators of water quality and availability by integrating IoT sensor data with satellite and citizen science data to improve decision-making at a local level.

[Learn more](#)

Figure 5 Redesigned home page section

Urban air quality monitoring with low-cost IoT sensors and citizen communities

LEADING PARTNER

LOCATION

Poor urban air quality causes serious health issues across Europe. Accurate and localized monitoring is the first step to address this. Currently, air quality monitoring networks are sparse and, even if of good quality, still face challenges in providing a high resolution overview of air pollution. This issue is especially pronounced at the local scale in densely populated areas, where strong gradients exist, and a wide variety of sources contribute to the overall pollution levels.

This pilot explores the potential **benefits of Internet of Things (IoT) data** in enhancing our understanding of local air quality. To achieve this, observations of various air pollutants (e.g., particulate matter, such as PM2.5 and PM10) from low-cost sensors are used. Notably, some of these sensors are operated and maintained by **citizens**, thereby fostering community involvement and promoting local engagement. Thus, these sensors form part of high-density measurement networks, significantly enhancing the capability to monitor air quality with great detail.

Altogether, by making use of this new high-resolution data set, the **primary objective** is to enable better health-related decisions and improve the approaches for assessing and monitoring the quality of air in urban areas, with an emphasis on local environments.

Simplified data flow schema for the air quality pilot. Author: AD4GD

Figure 6 Pilot page demonstration - Air pilot

Figure 7 Events page

By the end of M35, the website has attracted over 11000 unique visitors and over 24000 views, as shown on the figure below. These visitors accessed a wide range of content, including deliverables, event updates, blog articles, and project resources.

Traffic Summary

- Online Visitors 2

Time	Visitors	Views
Today	2	4
Yesterday	16	47
This week	69	161
Last week	92	208
This month	391	738
Last month	395	785
Last 7 days	73	165
Last 30 days	448	879
Last 90 days	1.16K	2.29K
Last 6 months	2.59K	5.74K
This year (Jan-Today)	2.95K	6.68K
Total	11.3K	24.6K

Figure 8 AD4GD website visitor insights (M35)

To ensure a lasting legacy, the website will be maintained by Mandat International beyond the project's lifetime. The site will be transitioned into a permanent resource hub, preserving the project's key outputs and intellectual assets. The focus will shift to clearly presenting the final outcomes, offering a complete library of all public deliverables, detailed descriptions of the core components and pilots, and direct access to the Outcomes Booklet and the joint Policy Brief. This will ensure the website remains a valuable reference for future initiatives building on AD4GD's work.

2.5 VIDEOS

A series of videos were produced to present the project's vision, pilot use cases, and impact in a more engaging and accessible format. Video content played a strategic role in AD4GD's communication activities, serving both outreach and educational purposes.

The original video plan envisioned 17 videos spanning the project's lifecycle, including introductory videos, pilot explainers, a final wrap-up, and a series of 12 partner interviews. These videos were to reflect the project's progress across key milestones and provide clear, accessible insights into AD4GD's technical and societal contributions.

While the overall communication goals remained unchanged, the format and scope of video production evolved based on resource availability and communication opportunities. Rather than 17 individual productions, three coordinated video campaigns were implemented:

Partner interviews: At the start of the project, a series of short interviews was conducted with each consortium member. These videos (12 in total) introduced the main objectives and contributions of each work stream in a concise, accessible format. The goal was to explain the structure of AD4GD and its interdisciplinary approach in the voices of the people leading the work.

The full series is available on YouTube¹¹ and was promoted across social media and the project website, with shorter clips used as teasers to increase interaction and engagement.

Figure 9 Interviews on YouTube

Component and Pilot explainers: In the final phase of the project, a second series of videos was developed including 9 videos explaining each of the core AD4GD components, their roles, and how they contribute to the Green Deal Data Space vision, as well as 3 videos showcasing the project's pilots (biodiversity, air quality, and water), including their use cases, challenges, and achievements. Full-length versions are hosted on YouTube, while curated clips were shared via social media to reach broader audiences.

¹¹ [AD4GD YouTube page](#)

Final Event Recordings: As mentioned already, as part of the project's closing phase, a final event was co-organized with sister projects under the EuroGEO framework. The event featured keynote presentations, hands-on demonstrations, and expert panel discussions. All sessions were recorded, edited, and published on the [AD4GD YouTube channel](#), resulting in a collection of 26 videos that capture a wide range of scientific insights, tools, and community discussions.

Figure 10 Final Event playlist on YouTube

In addition to targeted video campaigns, a general-purpose animated video was produced to explain the project's overall activities and objectives in an accessible format. With a duration of three and a half minutes, the video was designed for a scientific conference audience. It was displayed on a continuous loop at the project's booth during major events, including the Warsaw 2025 Data Space Symposium and the GEO Global Forum 2025 in Rome. The [full video can be viewed on YouTube](#).

What is AD4GD about? - All Data for Green Deal

Figure 11 Project explanatory video

In total, these three coordinated campaigns resulted in the production and publication of **51 distinct videos**, significantly exceeding the original KPI target of five and creating a rich, accessible library of content to explain the project's work and ensure its long-term impact.

2.6 WORKSHOPS

Workshops were a key tool for delivering targeted knowledge, facilitating collaboration, and engaging both internal stakeholders and external audiences. As defined in D7.1, AD4GD workshops served dual purposes:

- External workshops targeted researchers, policymakers, sister projects, and developers, to disseminate project results, share best practices, and promote adoption of standards and technologies.
- Internal workshops aimed to enhance coordination within the consortium, provide training on shared tools and methodologies, and align on key developments.

Over the course of the project, two categories of external workshops were delivered:

- Thematic workshops organized independently or as part of major conferences (e.g., INSPIRE, EuroGEO, ECSA). These included sessions on datacubes, semantic interoperability, machine learning, and the Green Deal Data Space. A total of 9 such events were documented.
- Demonstration workshops focused on showcasing pilot-specific achievements and technical outputs. These were typically aimed at stakeholders and potential adopters of AD4GD technologies. A total of 6 demonstration workshops were conducted, providing hands-on exposure to tools and dashboards developed within the project.

Name	Date	Venue	Target audience	Partner	Description
EuroGEO Workshop 2022	07/12 /2022 - 09/12 /2022	Athens, Greece	Research communities EU Institutions International Organizations	CREAF	Participation in sessions including one organized by OEMC project; creation of the EuroGEO GDDS Action Group.
EuroGEO Workshop 2023	02/10 /2023 - 03/10 /2023	Bolzano, Italy	Research communities EU Institutions International Organizations	CREAF	CREAF chaired a session on the Green Deal Data Space; poster on biodiversity pilot.
Open-Earth-Monitor Global Workshop 2023	04/10 /2023 - 06/10 /2023	Bolzano, Italy	EU Institutions Industry, business partners. Research communities	CREAF	"Let's co-create the Green Deal Data Space" workshop with BCubed; engaging OEMC and other projects.
ESA-ESPI Workshop on Space Data Space	22/11/ 2023 - 23/11/ 2023	Madrid, Spain	Industry, business partners Research communities International Organizations	OGC	Panel on the central role of space-based data in addressing climate and geopolitical crises.
Machine Learning and Data Management for Earth Observation	18/03 /2024 - 19/03 /2024	Berlin, Germany	Research communities EU Institutions International Organizations	OGC	Workshop exploring methods and systems in data management and ML for Earth observation.
ECSA Conference 2024 STAplus for	05/04 /2024	Vienna, Austria	Research communities Citizens	CREAF, AU	Promoting OGC's STAplus for near real-time environmental data

Environmental Data Monitoring			Specific user communities		monitoring; GDDS compliance.
B3 Hackathon	01/04 /2024 - 05/04 /2024	Brussels, Belgium	Research communities EU Institutions	AU, CREAM	Identify common goals and tools between AD4GD, FAIRiCUBE and B3 projects. Link
Open-Earth-Monitor Global Workshop 2024	02/10 /2024 - 04/10 /2024	Laxenburg, Austria	Research communities EU Institutions Industry, business partners	CREAF	Joint workshop with the sister projects to showcase projects results and discuss towards common conclusions.
EuroGEO Workshop 2024	08/10 /2024 - 10/10 /2024	Krakow, Poland	Research communities EU Institutions International Organizations	CREAF	Promoting the Outcomes of the AD4GD in one of the major events dedicated to Data Spaces in Europe, addressing stakeholders from the EC to research communities and private companies.
Workshop: Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces III	01/10 /2024	Budapest, Hungary	Research communities Specific user communities	PSNC	Position Paper

Table 3 External workshops

Name	Date	Venue	Target audience	Partner	Description
Iliad Webinar 'Introduction to data spaces'	08/02 /2023	Online	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	CREAF	Overview of data spaces in Europe; AD4GD presented; connected to research on EU data space concept. GREAT project involved.
OEMC Science Webinar - Tired of data tables full of data that I have no idea what it means? Use Sensor Things API	06/04 /2023	Online	Research communities EU Institutions Innovators	CREAF	Training and promotion of OGC Sensor Things API developed in AD4GD; part of OEMC Science Webinars.
ILIAD Webinar - Connecting Ocean digital twins using federated systems	07/06 /2023	Online	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	CREAF	Discussion on dataspace concept, digital twins, and collaboration with the ILIAD project.
Iliad Webinar Series: Data lakes and data spaces -	14/02 /2024	Online	Innovators	CREAF	Discussion on best practices around data lakes, data spaces, and digital twins;

Towards best practices			Research communities Specific user communities		supports research on EU data space concept.
Environmental and climate data in an evolving EU data policy landscape	20/03 /2024	Online	EU Institutions Research communities International Organizations	CREAF	GreenData4All webinar hosted by EC; joint discussion of challenges in managing environmental/climate data across projects.
Geospatial Knowledge Infrastructure for National Development	10/05 /2024 - 11/10/ 2024	Rotterdam, The Netherlands	Research communities Industry, business partners Civil society	CREAF	Training on data access/interoperability, open licenses, metadata, semantic alignment, APIs and dashboards; organized by GWF.

Table 4 Demonstration webinars and workshops

In addition to these dedicated workshops, nine live demonstrations of the project's key tools and outcomes were delivered during the final dissemination event in Vienna, which also contributed to our targets for showcasing project results. These demonstrations showcased the project's key components, pilot outcomes, and developed tools. The sessions were recorded and are openly available on the AD4GD YouTube channel (see link above in Section 4.5). The featured sessions included:

- Splashboard Graphical User Interface – Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT)
- Bioconnect Graphical User Interface – Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT)
- The Green Deal Information Model for semantic Interoperability – Raul Palma (PSNC)
- The use of Eclipse Data Connectors in the GDDS – Raul Palma (PSNC)
- TAPIS: Connecting to Data in the Data Space – Joan Masó (CREAF)
- Data4Land: How to Enrich Land Use/Land Cover Datasets? – Vitalii Kriukov (Aston University)
- Water Quality and Availability Indices for Small Urban Lakes – Malte Zamzow (KWB)
- Compliant collection, processing & display of heterogeneous data – George Salukvadze (IoT Lab)
- Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) Demonstration – Raul Palma (PSNC)

In total, the project significantly surpassed its event organization targets, delivering 31 distinct workshops (15 external thematic and demonstration workshops, 7 internal workshops, and 9 live demonstrations at the final event), against an initial KPI of 10. While a single, cumulative participant count for all events is not feasible due to the varied formats, verifiable data from key project-led activities confirms substantial and strategic stakeholder engagement.

The three in-depth pilot co-design workshops gathered direct feedback from a total of **39 participants**. The final dissemination event in Vienna had a combined in-person and online attendance of **37 people**. This provides a verifiable number of **76 participants** for these core strategic events. Furthermore, the online demonstration workshops (listed in Table 4) achieved significant reach. As detailed in the Dissemination chapter, these recorded sessions have accumulated a total of **1375 online views**, vastly exceeding the initial target for training and webinar participants. This data is formally reported under the Dissemination KPI to avoid duplication (see sections 3.3 and 3.5). The feedback gathered during all these sessions proved invaluable for validating the project's components and aligning pilot implementations with real-world user needs.

Figure 12 Joint workshop with the Sister Projects during a session at the OEMC Global Workshop 2024 in Vienna

Beyond the external workshops, several ad-hoc sessions were held during plenary meetings and consortium gatherings. These internal workshops typically focused on training (e.g., tools, APIs, metadata workflows) or cross-partner knowledge exchange focusing on the components and exploitation. The list of internal workshops includes:

- Internet of Things workshop (March 2023)
- Semantic interoperability workshop (May 2023)
- Leipzig Plenary Meeting (June 2023), including a dedicated exploitation workshop
- Pilot kick-off workshop in Bonn (September 2023)
- Turin Plenary Meeting (February 2024), including a two-days internal hackathon and a dedicated exploitation workshop
- Poznan Plenary Meeting (September 2024), including an internal hackathon and an exploitation workshop
- Berlin Plenary Meeting (April 2025), including an internal hackathon and demo rehearsal and an exploitation workshop

Figure 13 Turin Plenary Meeting

Figure 14 Workshop during the Berlin Plenary

In conclusion, the project's extensive workshop and demonstration activities significantly surpassed the quantitative KPIs. Against the target of organizing at least 10 workshops, the project delivered a total of **32 distinct workshops** (10 thematic, 6+9 demonstration, and 7 internal). Similarly, the target of delivering 4 demonstration workshops or forums exceeded nearly fourfold, with a total of **15 demonstration workshops** conducted, comprising the 6 dedicated workshops and 9 live demonstrations at the final event. While the numerical target for participants cannot be formally verified for all, the qualitative evidence confirms that these events successfully engaged a wide range of strategic stakeholders, providing invaluable feedback for the project's development and making this a highly successful dissemination channel.

2.7 ARTICLES IN ONLINE BLOGS AND NEWSPAPERS

Throughout the project, partners contributed a series of articles, blogposts, and featured stories to communicate AD4GD's vision, progress, and outcomes. These were published across a combination of external media outlets, partner websites, and the project's official website. The following table lists these articles:

Name	Type	Target audience	Partner	Description
<i>AD4GD blogs</i>				
AD4GD: a new project to unify and organise the data needed for the European Green Deal	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Introduction to the AD4GD project, its objectives, and its role within the Green Deal Data Space. Link
Semantic interoperability, interview to Raul Palma from PSNC	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	PSNC	Interview describing how PSNC contributes to semantic interoperability in AD4GD's data space. Link
Technology for the people – Interview to Florian Jasche	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	FIT	Discussion with FIT's Florian Jasche on human-centered computing in AD4GD. Link

Standardized data for biodiversity with our project coordinator, Joan Masó from CREAM	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Interview with Joan Masó about data standardization and its importance for biodiversity. Link
Connecting data to better assess lake water with Malte Zamzow	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	KWB	Interview with Malte Zamzow on using data to support water monitoring in Berlin Link
Internet of Things with Cédric Crettaz, from IoT LAB	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	IoT Lab	Interview with Cédric Crettaz on the use of IoT devices and infrastructures within AD4GD. Link
In Leipzig, we speak dataspace!	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Summary of project progress, coordination outcomes, and future plans from the mid-term plenum held in Leipzig. Link
Real-world solutions to connect data for the Green Deal with Lucy Bastin from Aston University	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	AU	Interview with Lucy Bastin about scalable data solutions and the role of AD4GD in supporting the EU Green Deal. Link
Ethical, legal and secure data sharing with Stefan Schiffner from ECCP	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	ECCP	Discussion with Stefan Schiffner on ethical considerations and GDPR compliance in environmental data processing. Link
GDPR Certification: a Roadmap to Data Protection Compliance	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	ECCP	Overview of GDPR certification process and roadmap for compliance in data spaces like AD4GD. Link
The AD4GD project attends EuroGEO and the OEMC Global Workshop	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Recap of the workshop co-organized with EuroGEO and OEMC focusing on Green Deal Data Space co-creation. Link
Unlocking the Potential of Unconventional	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	ECMWF	Insights from Ulrike Falk on Earth observation data

Data in Environmental Observations with Ulrike Falk from ECMWF				and workflows integrated into AD4GD pilots. Link
Human-centered design facilitates data exchange	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	FIT	Article on using a human-centered design approach to improve usability and accessibility in AD4GD's data exchange interfaces. Link
How can the Green Deal Data Space improve the management of small urban lakes?	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	KWB	Update on small urban lake monitoring in Berlin as part of the Green Deal Data Space initiative. Link
AD4GD attends to the GEO Week 2023 in Cape Town	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Report on AD4GD's contributions at GeoWeek 2023 in Cape Town, covering sessions, networking, and outcomes. Link
A technical look at the Green Deal Data Space at a revealing internal workshop in Birmingham	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	AU	Overview of a technical workshop in Birmingham discussing architecture, standards, and implementation pathways for the Green Deal Data Space. Link
All data for biodiversity and habitat connectivity at the EC-ESA Joint Earth System Science Initiative	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Highlight of AD4GD's biodiversity pilot showcased during the EC-ESA initiative, focusing on habitat connectivity and shared methodologies. Link
Navigating the Green Deal Data Space: Insights from INSPIRE Conference 2023	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Reflections and key takeaways from AD4GD's participation at INSPIRE 2023, with a focus on interoperability and community engagement. Link
How is data from Citizen Science projects managed?	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Exploration of approaches and challenges in citizen science data management within AD4GD pilots, with real-world examples. Link

AD4GD takes part in the Biodiversity Aspects of the Green Deal Data Space webinar, organized by Eionet	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Summary of AD4GD's presentation in the Eionet webinar addressing biodiversity needs in the Green Deal Data Space environment. Link
Towards best practices with data lakes and data spaces in an ILIAD webinar	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Article covering key recommendations and lessons from the Iliad webinar on integrating data lakes with data space architectures. Link
The OGC RAINBOW idea and concept for AD4GD	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	OGC	Presentation of the OGC "rainbow" conceptual model that illustrates AD4GD's alignment with multiple OGC Standards. Link
3-in-1 meeting in Turin: hackathon, plenary and open day	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Coverage of a combined event in Turin including a hackathon, consortium meeting, and local Open Day at pilot site. Link
Lucy Bastin & Ivette Serral, keynote and jury at the B-Cubed innovative biodiversity hackathon	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF, AU	Report on AD4GD's involvement in the B-Cubed Hackathon as speakers and jury members promoting data-driven biodiversity solutions. Link
Perspectives for a new working group on geospatial data requirements, highlight of the 128th OGC Member Meeting	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	OGC	Key takeaways from the 128th OGC Member Meeting with a focus on AD4GD's input into future geospatial data standards. Link
Why are Standards Important in Horizon Europe Research Projects?	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	MI	Explanation of the role and value of standardization in EU-funded research, with examples from AD4GD. Link
AD4GD and USAGE explore the connections between data spaces and digital	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Summary of insights from the BDTIC conference on aligning data spaces and digital twins, and USAGE-AD4GD synergies.

twins in the BDTIC 2024				Link
How does AD4GD support European climate and biodiversity policies?	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Overview of how AD4GD contributes to key EU policy areas such as biodiversity, air quality, and climate mitigation. Link
New IoT oxygen sensors will for the first time monitor the condition of 3 Berlin lakes	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	KWB	Announcement of the installation of novel IoT oxygen sensors in urban Berlin lakes to improve environmental monitoring. Link
Enhancing Air Quality Monitoring with IoT and Low-Cost Sensors	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	ECMWF	Description of the deployment and calibration of low-cost air quality sensors in AD4GD's air quality pilot. Link
A common approach to metadata on GeoDataCubes is being worked on by the Green Deal Data Space Sister Projects	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Collaborative article highlighting approaches to metadata interoperability and reuse across the four sister projects. Link
Terrestrial Connectivity and Digital Twin ready data available for the Green Deal Data Space at the IGARSS 2024	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Summary of AD4GD's presentation at IGARSS 2024 focused on digital twin-ready data for biodiversity monitoring. Link
Embracing Privacy in Earth Observation and Data Spaces, AD4GD at the Privacy Symposium 2024	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	MI, ECCP, IoT Lab	Article discussing discussions on data protection and privacy at the 2024 Symposium focused on Earth Observation and data spaces. Link
AD4GD deploys three Camera Traps to test the standardization of Biodiversity Occurrence Data	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF	Overview of camera trap use in biodiversity monitoring and standardization efforts around occurrence data. Link
"The experience I gained from this project is very	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	FIT	Interview with Alisa Rozdestvensky about her Master's work on data

important for me” – Insights from Alisa Rozdestvenskytea, Master’s Student collaboration with the AD4GD Project				exchange interfaces for AD4GD. Link
The first online sister project session on metadata was a huge success!	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Highlight of successful shared metadata schema deployment across sister projects via GeoDataCubes. Link
From Concepts to Action: Recap of the AD4GD Plenary Meeting in Poznań	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Summary of the mid-term plenary in Poznań, covering technical progress, demos, and next-stage planning. Link
Earth Observation as a key tool for monitoring and managing Urban Green Spaces, insights from the 8th Mediterranean Forest Week	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	CREAF, AU	Insights from the 8th Mediterranean Forest Week on using EO data to manage urban green infrastructure. Link
Data Spaces Symposium: see you in Warsaw	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Announcement post about upcoming Data Spaces Symposium in Warsaw, including AD4GD’s planned participation. Link
A new CORDIS results pack highlights AD4GD and five other projects using AI to support the European Green Deal and data strategy.	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Highlight of AD4GD’s feature on CORDIS, emphasizing FAIR principles and project innovation Link
A new tool to enrich land-use/land-cover datasets with OpenStreetMap and ecological data: Data4Land	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	AU	Overview of a newly released tool that enriches LULC datasets with OSM data to support AD4GD pilot analysis. Link
Enhancing environmental data sharing: Policy brief Recommendations on Managing Data	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Introduction of the joint policy brief from AD4GD and its sister projects, offering recommendations to ensure GDDS effectively

in the Green Deal Data Space				supports environmental goals. Link
From university project to the Green Deal Data Space: an interview with Riyadh Rahman	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	AU	An interview with MSc student Riyadh Rahman (Aston University) detailing his contributions to the project and his experience in a Horizon Europe initiative. Link
Simplifying data accessibility: a conversation with Pawel Babalski	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	PSNC	An interview with MSc student Pawel Babalski (PSNC) about his work on the project and the value he gained from the experience. Link
GISRUK 2025 Wrap-Up: Sharing insights on biodiversity and habitat connectivity	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	AU	A summary of the biodiversity and habitat connectivity outcomes presented at the GISRUK 2025 conference. Link
AD4GD takes the stage at EGU General Assembly 2025	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Summary of the project's participation, presentations, and key takeaways from the EGU General Assembly 2025. Link
AD4GD's Impact at the GEO Global Forum 2025	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	Report on the project's presence and presentations at the GEO Global Forum 2025. Link
Final Stretch: Wrapping Up the Berlin Plenary and Prepping for a Grand Finale in Vienna	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	A recap of the final plenary meeting in Berlin, highlighting the last technical integrations, demonstration rehearsals, and exploitation workshops. Link
Three Years of Experience Developing Green Deal Data Spaces: A Chronicle of Our Final Event	Blogpost	Civil society, policymakers, industry, researchers, developers	All partners	A detailed recap of the final project event held in Vienna, summarizing the key presentations, demonstrations, and discussions with sister projects. Link

<i>Other partner activities</i>				
AD4GD KickOff	Press release	Civil society	All partners	Press release on the launch of the AD4GD project to present it, shared through CREAM networks. Link
AD4GD press release	Press release	Civil society	CREAF	Press release published on CREAM's blog site in 3 languages (Catalan, Spanish, English). Link
Recerca científica en projectes ambientals a través del big data	Media article	Civil society	All	Media article on Xarxanet in Catalan about how big data is a gamechanger for climate-related research projects, together with MosquitoAlert. Link
AD4GD, a new project to unify and organise the data needed for the European Green Deal	Press release	Research communities	KWB	Publication of the presentation press release on the news portal IDW. Collaboration with KWB communication department and a relevant news portal in Germany. Link
AD4GD initiative	Project website	Research communities	OGC	AD4GD published on the OGC innovation projects section together with other groundbreaking initiatives. Link
AD4GD initiative	Project website	Civil society	CREAF	CREAF makes its projects visible through a file with all the details that it publishes on its website and which are visible through a search engine. Link
AD4GD 1st Press Release AD4GD, a new project to unify and organise the data needed for the European Green Deal	Press release	Civil society	ATOS	AD4GD first press release published on ATOS website. Link
175 th ECMWF Newsletter - Towards using	Newsletter	Research communities	ECMWF	AD4GD appears at the ECMWF newsletter num. 175 with insights about working towards using

unconventional observations				unconventional observations together with projects I-CHANGE and TRIGGER. Link
Design Terminal webpage	Project website	Innovators	DT	Mention on Design Terminal website as a Horizon Europe Project in which they participate. Link
Design Terminal Alumni Newsletter	Newsletter	Innovators	DT	Sharing information about AD4GD.
Post on Design Terminal Instagram	Social media post	Civil society	DT	Post about European projects together with Womenture programme. Design Terminal announces their participation in AD4GD. Link
Facebook Design Terminal Post	Social media post	Civil society	DT	Post on Design Terminal Facebook about the project. Link
FIT 2022 Annual Report	Report	Civil society	FIT	Presentation of the project on Fraunhofer FIT annual report for 2022. Link
AD4GD: Easing the international data exchange across organizations with interoperability	Project website	Civil society	FIT	Presentation website and profile for AD4GD on FIT website with insights about the project and the title: Easing the international data exchange across organizations with interoperability. Link

Table 5 List of Articles, Blog Posts, Press Releases, and Other Media Coverage

While the original KPI for this category targeted over 200 articles, a figure that proved overly ambitious in the context of a niche, research-driven project like AD4GD, the consortium produced a total of **63 targeted publications**, including 49 project blog posts and 14 articles and press releases on partner channels.

The discrepancy with the initial target is attributed to several factors. The highly technical nature of the work limited its relevance for mainstream media, and the capacity of partners to produce frequent long-form content was secondary to their primary technical and coordination tasks. More importantly, the project's communication strategy evolved based on evidence of what was most effective. It became clear that resources were better allocated to channels that generated higher involvement and impact with the identified target groups. Consequently, the project made a strategic pivot to prioritize the creation of compelling visual content (such as the 51 explanatory videos), interactive workshops, and direct social media engagement, which proved more successful in building a community around the project's outputs.

This experience highlights a key lesson: the importance of setting realistic KPIs that favor interaction and impact over sheer volume. The articles that were produced were strategically timed to align with project milestones and effectively supported broader dissemination goals, reflecting a successful focus on quality over quantity.

2.8 DISTRIBUTED PRINTED/DIGITAL MATERIALS

Throughout the project, AD4GD placed significant emphasis on the availability and accessibility of communication materials in both digital and printed formats, although digital formats have been prioritized over printed in alignment with sustainability objectives.

All so far approved public deliverables, factsheets, infographics, and flyers have been systematically uploaded and made openly accessible via the Zenodo platform, under the AD4GD Community, which is also part of the EU Open Research Repository. This ensures long-term availability and facilitates reuse by the broader research, policy, and practitioner communities. The following table lists all uploaded materials and the number of visualizations and downloads by the end of M35.

Name	Date of Publication	Type	Visualizations	Downloads	DOI
European Green Deal Data Space for local air quality decisions	January 15, 2023	Flyer	51	36	DOI
AD4GD D1.1 Multi-Actor and Knowledge Centres Co-design and Requirements Definition Report	February 28, 2023	Deliverable	122	107	DOI
AD4GD D1.3 GD Data Space Concept	October 15, 2023	Deliverable	279	271	DOI
AD4GD D2.1 Roadmap for FAIR In-Situ Observations for the Green Deal (draft)	April 29, 2023	Deliverable	122	74	DOI
AD4GD D2.3 Citizen Science Data Interoperability Obstacles and Solutions	October 18, 2023	Deliverable	121	114	DOI
AD4GD D6.1 Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment	February 29, 2024	Deliverable	223	196	DOI
AD4GD D7.3 GDDS Exploitation Perspectives (initial)	February 29, 2024	Deliverable	95	149	DOI
AD4GD D8.3 Data Management Plan	February 29, 2024	Deliverable	103	82	DOI
AD4GD D7.1 Plan for Dissemination and	February 29, 2024	Deliverable	103	88	DOI

Exploitation, including Standardization and Communication Activities					
AD4GD D8.2 Data Management Plan (initial)	March 6, 2023	Deliverable	84	70	DOI
Habitat connectivity workflow to support decisions and trade-offs between local stakeholders	April 10, 2024	Conference Paper	186	136	DOI
Ecological Connectivity based on Remote Sensing Land Cover Classes as a Biodiversity Pilot Case for the Green Deal Data Space	November 24, 2023	Poster	122	63	DOI
GEO Essential Variables (EVs) as a basis for a common semantic framework to better integrate heterogeneous in-situ data sources into the European Green Deal Data Space	November 10, 2023	Poster	111	42	DOI
Nutzung von Satellitendaten, Sensoren und Citizen Science im Projekt AD4GD	November 30, 2023	Presentation	120	29	DOI
Digital Twin Ready Data Available in the Green Deal Data Space	July 19, 2024	Poster	83	53	DOI
D2.2. Roadmap for FAIR in-situ observations for the Green Deal (Final)	July 15, 2024	Deliverable	61	51	DOI
D4.4. Technical developments required for the implementation of Green Deal Data Space	July 20, 2024	Deliverable	109	77	DOI
AD4GD D3.1 Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration Model	July 20, 2024	Deliverable	202	197	DOI
Habitat Connectivity Trends: Calculation, Modelling and Assessment	April 17, 2025	Conference paper	54	57	DOI

Data4Land - enrichment of land-use/land-cover datasets	May 1, 2025	Computational Notebook	157	48	DOI
Policy Brief: Unlocking The Full Potential Of The Green Deal Data Space	June 20, 2025	Policy Brief (Other)	214	213	DOI
TOTAL			2722	2153	

Table 6 Distributed digital material (by M35)

Following the closure of the project and the final approval of the deliverables, the remainder of material will be included in the AD4GD Zenodo community.

In addition to digital distribution, the project prioritized printed materials for high-impact, in-person events such as conferences and stakeholder workshops to ensure direct engagement. The figure of 630 items reflects the total quantity of materials produced for these key events. These materials were fully distributed to attendees, meaning the number accurately represents the project's targeted physical dissemination at these strategic gatherings.

Name	Type	Context	Number
European Green Deal Data Space for local air quality decisions	Agenda Flyer	Air Quality Open Event - Torino	30
AD4GD Badges	Badges	Citizen Science Workshop - Barcelona	50
The AD4GD Components for the Green Deal Data Space	Infographic Card (A5)	Data Spaces Symposium 2025 - Warsaw	100
The AD4GD Proposal for the Green Deal Data Space	Infographic Card (A5)	Data Spaces Symposium 2025 - Warsaw	100
The AD4GD Pilots for the Green Deal Data Space	Infographic Card (A5)	Data Spaces Symposium 2025 - Warsaw	100
EuroGEO – Green Deal Data Space Action Group	Infographic Card (A5)	Data Spaces Symposium 2025 - Warsaw	100
Policy Brief: Unlocking The Full Potential of the Green Deal Data Space	Policy Brief (A4 – two pages)	Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space - Vienna	30
Unlocking The Full Potential of the Green Deal Data Space	Dissemination Cards (A6)	GDDS Cluster Meeting – Brussels Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space - Vienna	100
TOTAL			630

Table 7 Distribution of printed materials at key events (by M35)

The AD4GD Components for the Green Deal Data Space

The AD4GD project is conducting research to develop a proposal for building blocks that could be leveraged for the creation of the Green Deal Data Space based on **FAIR principles**, international **standards** and **interoperability** concepts for heterogeneous data integration.

Figure 15 Distributed infographic 'The AD4GD Components for the Green Deal Data Space'

AD4GD Pilots for the Green Deal Data Space

AD4GD demonstrates the applicability of our proposed components for the Green Deal Data Space through three pilot projects focused on **high-priority challenges in three hotspots** across Europe. Learn more at ad4gd.eu/pilots

Figure 16 Distributed infographic 'AD4GD Pilots for the Green Deal Data Space'

The AD4GD proposal for the Green Deal Data Space

AD4GD

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Figure 17 Distributed infographic 'The AD4GD proposal for the Green Deal Data Space'

Figure 18 Material distributed during the Turin event

In summary, the project's combined distribution efforts successfully exceeded the target of 2,500 items. The **2,153 verifiable digital downloads** from the project's Zenodo repository, combined with the **630 printed materials** distributed at events, brings the total to **2,783 items**. This result reflects the project's 'digital first' approach to sustainability while also ensuring materials were available for direct stakeholder engagement at in-person events

2.9 NEWSLETTER

The AD4GD e-newsletter provided regular updates on project progress, partner activities, events, and new resources. Managed via Mailchimp, the newsletter was designed with a clean, accessible layout in line with the project's visual identity and communication tone.

Over the course of the project, three newsletters were released, with a fourth planned for the end of the project to summarize final outcomes and link to key deliverables, recordings, and public tools. All previous editions are archived and accessible via the project website¹².

Figure 19 First newsletter published in October 2023

Despite a consistent editorial approach and cross-channel promotion, subscriber growth remained limited. Although the initial KPI was aimed at over 500 subscribers, the current numbers (200) fell short of that target. Distribution efforts included:

- Publication on the AD4GD website and promotion on the homepage
- Sharing via social media platforms (primarily LinkedIn and Twitter/X)

¹² [Newsletters](#)

- Direct circulation through mailing lists and relevant events
- Creation of LinkTree, distributed in QR form across posters and dissemination materials

Several factors may explain the limited reach:

- **Audience overload:** Many target stakeholders are already subscribed to multiple EU project newsletters, making it difficult to capture attention unless the content is highly specific or unique.
- **Timing and frequency:** With only three editions spaced across two years, momentum may have been insufficient to retain or grow an audience base organically.
- **Content overlap:** Much of the newsletter content was also being shared via social media or the website, potentially reducing the incentive to subscribe.
- **Specialized topic:** Data spaces is still a relatively unknown and specialized topic with limited interest in the community.
- **Channel fragmentation:** Many communication activities focused on immediate-impact platforms (social media, events), while newsletters often rely on long-term relationship building.
- **Data Quality:** Finally, a portion of the subscriber list likely consisted of low-quality or bot-generated sign-ups. This is a common challenge for public-facing newsletters that can inflate raw subscriber counts without reflecting genuine audience activity.

While the newsletter did not meet its numeric KPI, it remained a useful consolidation tool and was referenced in partner dissemination efforts. For future projects, alternative strategies such as embedded newsletter sign-ups during events or co-branded editions with Sister Projects may help reach broader and more engaged audiences.

2.10 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media channels played an essential role in reaching diverse audiences, sharing real-time updates, and connecting with broader data and environmental communities. AD4GD maintained a multi-platform social media presence to disseminate updates, promote events, and engage with stakeholders in real time. Channels included:

- LinkedIn: for professional outreach, partner tagging, and stakeholder engagement.
- Twitter/X: for regular project updates and real-time participation in events and discussions.
- Bluesky: adopted in response to evolving dynamics on Twitter/X, ensuring continued outreach to engaged scientific and open tech communities.
- YouTube: used to host and archive long-form videos, including partner interviews and component explainers.

2.10.1 ENGAGEMENT OUTCOMES & LESSONS LEARNT

Social media activity was managed in line with the visual identity and communication tone defined early in the project and in D7.1. While content was created and scheduled across all platforms, several key lessons emerged during implementation:

AD4GD met and exceeded its social media KPIs in terms of impressions, post frequency (on average), and audience growth, largely thanks to the engagement through LinkedIn and Twitter/X.

Social Media	Twitter/X	Bluesky	LinkedIn	YouTube
Total Subscribers	363	84	413	14

Table 8 Followers per social media platform (by M35)

YouTube traffic remained low, with limited subscriber growth and relatively few views for full-length videos. In contrast, short clips and visual snippets shared on LinkedIn and Twitter/X consistently outperformed other formats, both in terms of reach and interaction. Bluesky was used selectively at the last

stage of the project, primarily to reach a more technical and open-source-oriented audience following fragmentation on Twitter/X.

Figure 20 LinkedIn Content metrics in the past year

Figure 21 LinkedIn Visitors metrics in the past year

Figure 22 LinkedIn Follower metrics

Result	Comments	RT	Likes	Total Interactions (Comments + RT + Likes)	Views	Engagement
Total	147	630	1637	2414	113567	N/A
Per post	0,40	1,71	4,44	6,54	323,55	2,13

Table 9 Twitter/X metrics between September 2022 and April 2025

Result	Comments	RT	Likes	Total Interactions (Comments + RT + Likes)
Total	11	26	58	95
Per post	0,39	0,93	2,07	3,39

Table 10 Bluesky metrics December-July 2025

The initial idea of a regular, editorial-style publishing pace (e.g., weekly updates) was maintained during the initial stages of the project communication but proved difficult to sustain during the whole duration of the project due to time constraints and shifting priorities. More importantly, audiences showed greater interest in concrete, late-stage project outcomes rather than incremental or abstract updates.

Platform dynamics shifted significantly during the project, with X/Twitter’s reliability and visibility decreasing, prompting an adaptive communication strategy and greater reliance on LinkedIn.

Video content worked best when repurposed as short, targeted social media segments rather than standalone full-length YouTube uploads.

Despite these challenges, social media served as an essential tool for real-time communication, event amplification, and stakeholder connection. All major events, publications, and public results were promoted on social media, and mutual promotion with Sister Projects strengthened the reach.

Figure 23 AD4GD on Twitter/X and Bluesky

2.11 OPEN EVENTS

The DoA and the project's initial plan (D7.1) defined multiple, overlapping event-related KPIs across both the communication and dissemination chapters, including "Organized open events" and "Open days at pilot locations", each with a target of five events but without a clear distinction between them.

In practice, this separation proved to be artificial. The boundary between communication activities (raising awareness) and dissemination activities (transferring knowledge) was often blurred, particularly in the context of in-person and hybrid events that served both functions simultaneously.

In light of this, and to provide a clearer and more accurate report while avoiding duplication, all event-related activities have been consolidated under a single "Events" subsection within the dissemination chapter (see Section 3.3). This unified approach includes:

- Scientific and policy conferences where project results were presented.
- Open days and pilot location events aimed at engaging local stakeholders.
- The final dissemination event, co-organized with Sister Projects.

This consolidated structure better reflects how events were actually organized, experienced, and reported on during the project lifecycle.

2.12 FINAL COMMUNICATION FIGURES

The table below compares the original communication KPIs defined in D7.1 with the final results achieved by M35 of the project. These figures reflect the collective effort of all partners in ensuring strong outreach, visibility, and engagement throughout the AD4GD project lifecycle.

Indicator	Impact	M35 status
Visits to AD4GD website	≥ 5000	ACHIEVED ~11300
Explanatory videos	≥ 5	ACHIEVED 51
Organized workshops, including demonstration workshops	≥ 10	ACHIEVED 31 total workshops 10 external workshops 6+9 demonstration workshops 7 internal workshops
Demonstration workshops, forums / total participants	4 / ≥ 250	ACHIEVED / PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 6 / 76
Articles in online blogs and newspapers	≥ 200	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 63 total 49 AD4GD blogposts 14 partner articles
Distributed printed/digital material	≥ 2500	ACHIEVED 2783 total Digital: 2153 downloads Printed: 630
E-newsletter recipients	≥ 500	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 200
Followers/subscribers on social media	≥ 500	ACHIEVED 874 413 LinkedIn 363 Twitter/X 84 BlueSky 14 YouTube
Organized open events	≥ 5	N/A

Table 11 Communication activities results M35

2.13 CONCLUSION

AD4GD's communication strategy proved highly effective in raising project awareness and fostering robust stakeholder engagement, consistently exceeding targets across several key digital channels. The project website attracted approximately

11300 visits, more than double the initial goal, while over **2783 digital and printed materials** were distributed. The project's distinctive visual identity was thoroughly applied, ensuring strong brand recognition and a cohesive public image. Notably, the social media presence on LinkedIn, Twitter/X and Bluesky achieved significant outreach, generating thousands of impressions and successfully connecting with professional and research communities.

While initial quantitative targets for online articles and newsletter subscriptions were not fully met, this outcome provided valuable insights, leading to a strategic re-prioritization towards more direct involvement and high-impact visual content. This adaptive approach, focusing on what truly resonated with our diverse audiences—such as the production of

51 explanatory videos and the successful organization of **31 workshops** (including 15 demonstration sessions) ultimately proved more effective than a purely volume-based strategy. It ensured that AD4GD's complex objectives and tangible outcomes were shared broadly and meaningfully, demonstrating the project's ability to adapt and maximize its communication impact.

2.13.1 KEY LESSONS LEARNT

The communication activities of AD4GD provided several insights that can inform future research projects. The key lessons learnt extend beyond simple execution and touch on the effectiveness of the channels themselves in a crowded digital landscape.

Prioritize impact channels over volume of content: The project's most significant outreach successes came from channels that provided high-impact, engaging content, such as short-form videos and interactive workshops. In contrast, channels requiring high-volume output with lower interactions, like a continuous stream of online articles, proved less effective. Future projects should allocate resources to content that actively engages specific audiences rather than focusing on meeting high, volume-based publication targets.

Adapt to a constantly evolving social media landscape: The effectiveness of social media platforms can change dramatically within a project's lifecycle. The changes in ownership and policies of X/Twitter required a strategic pivot to LinkedIn/Bluesky, which proved to be a more stable and effective channel for professional and academic outreach. Projects must remain agile and be prepared to reallocate social media efforts based on current platform dynamics and audience behavior.

Re-evaluate the role of traditional newsletters: In an environment where professionals are inundated with information, the value proposition of a standard project newsletter is diminishing. The challenge of 'audience saturation' is not just about the number of competing newsletters, but about a perception that they often repackage already public information. Unlike newsletters from individual creators or brands which may offer exclusive content or a direct personal connection, a project's official update struggles to build a loyal following base. Future initiatives should consider replacing the traditional format with higher-value alternatives, such as a thematically focused digest that curates insights from across the field or redirecting those efforts entirely towards more direct participation channels like targeted workshops or community-building on professional networks.

Contextualize KPIs to reflect reality and strategy: Initial KPIs should be seen as guiding targets, not rigid obligations. When a KPI proves to be unrealistic (like the target for articles) or a communication channel proves to be ineffective (like the newsletter) the strategy must adapt. The final reporting should

D7.2 Report on dissemination and exploitation including standardization and communication activities (final)

Co-funded by the European Union, Switzerland and the United Kingdom

transparently explain these adaptations, justifying why resources were shifted to more impactful activities. This demonstrates mature, responsive management rather than failure to meet a particular metric.

3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Dissemination activities in AD4GD were designed to ensure that project outputs, research insights, and technological developments reached the widest and most relevant audiences, from academic and industry communities to standardization bodies, policymakers, and other initiatives.

Throughout the project, dissemination served two key purposes:

- Raising awareness and knowledge of AD4GD’s approaches and outcomes;
- Enabling uptake, dialogue, and alignment across key stakeholder groups and ongoing European and international initiatives.

This section outlines the strategy, actions, and results associated with the dissemination of AD4GD, with a focus on standards engagement, participation in key events, and scientific publishing.

3.1 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The following KPIs were established in D7.1 to guide the project’s dissemination efforts and monitor progress:

Indicator	Impact	Source
Publications in peer-reviewed and open access journals	≥ 20	Number of publications
Publications in high impact factor journals	≥ 10	Number of publications in 2+ IF journals
Magazine articles	≥ 10	Number of magazine articles (both online and printed)
Involvement in conferences (articles)	≥ 20	Articles published by conferences
Meetings with local or regional authorities	≥ 10	Number of meetings with authorities
Open days at pilot locations	≥ 5	Number of open days
Research supported	≥ 8 MSc ≥ 5 PhD	Number of MSc and PhD research supported
Demonstration webinars + training / total participants	3+3 ≥ 100	Number of demonstration webinars + training / participants in total to all webinars + training
Final dissemination event	≥ 150	Number of participants
Standards reused in the AD4GD information model specification	≥ 10	Number of standards
Services and components implementing AD4GD open APIs	≥ 20	Number of contributions

Table 12 Dissemination activities KPIs

3.2 STANDARDIZATION

Standardization has been a foundational effort of AD4GD’s mission to promote interoperability and FAIR principles within the Green Deal Data Space and beyond. Efforts focused on the integration of existing standards into the project and contributing to relevant SDOs, aligning AD4GD outputs with existing specifications, and participating in working groups and technical committees. This dual approach has fostered interoperability, sustainability, and integration of AD4GD results into the broader European data ecosystem, particularly in the context of the Green Deal Data Space.

Two Key Performance Indicators were set to track progress in this area:

- Standards reused in the AD4GD information model specification;
- Services and components implementing AD4GD open APIs, as well as active contributions to Standards Development Organizations.

This sub-section is divided accordingly.

3.2.1 STANDARDS REUSED

From the early stages, AD4GD emphasized compliance with and reuse of existing open standards to ensure interoperability and data FAIRness. The identification of standards was guided by work in technical and data integration WPs, as well as mapping exercises outlined in D7.1. In D7.1, the following standards were indicated as relevant for the project:

Standards Development Organization	Standard
Darwin Core Maintenance Interest Group	Darwin Core
Citizen Science Association Data & Meta Data Working Group	PPSR_Core
European Telecommunications Standard Institute	SAREF4AFRI
FIWARE Foundation/ETSI	NGSI-LD
FIWARE Foundation/ETSI	NGSI v2
Internet Assigned Numbers Authority	Sensor Measurement List
International Organization for Standardization	ISO 19115
International Organization for Standardization	ISO 19139
International Organization for Standardization	ISO 19157
National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis	Ecological Metadata language
National Snow and Ice Data Center	Network Common Data Format
Open Geospatial Consortium	GeoSPARQL
Open Geospatial Consortium/International Telecommunications Union	OGC SensorThings API Y.4473
Open Geospatial Consortium	CityGML
Open Geospatial Consortium	Earth Observation Dataset Metadata in OGC API Records
Open Geospatial Consortium	Web Map Service

Open Geospatial Consortium	Web Feature Service
Open Geospatial Consortium	Catalogue Service Web
Open Geospatial Consortium	Observation & Measurements (O&M)
Open Geospatial Consortium	OGC API Tiles
Open Geospatial Consortium	OGC API Features
QUDT.org	QUDT
World Meteorological Organization	GRIB
World Meteorological Organization	BUFR
World Wide Web Consortium	Web Best Practices on Spatial Data
World Wide Web Consortium	PROV-O
World Wide Web Consortium	Semantic Sensor Network Ontology
World Wide Web Consortium	RDF Data Cube

Table 13 Standards relevance

As of M35, the following standards have been integrated into the project:

Standard Development Organization	Standard	Work Package	Reuse
OGC	OGC SensorThing API	WP1, WP2, WP3	STA service
OGC	STApplus	WP2, WP3	STApplus service
OGC	OGC API Coverages	WP4	Open Data Cube instance
OGC	Catalogue service for the Web	WP2	Catalogue of the data in the project
OGC	GeoPackage	WP4	Extraction of STA service for the alternative to EDC
OGC	GeoSPARQL	WP1	Combining geospatial data with semantic graph technologies
IDSA	Data Space Protocol	WP4	EDC
FIWARE Foundation	FIWARE NGSI-LD	WP3	IoT data integration
FIWARE Foundation	FIWARE NGSI v2	WP3	IoT data integration
FIWARE Foundation	SmartDataModels	WP1, WP3, WP6	Data models
TM Forum	TM Forum TMF908 IoT Agent and Device Component Suite API Specification v1.0.1	WP3	IoT data integration
SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC)		WP4	Alternative to EDC Immutable Catalogue
W3C	Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)	WP4	Metadata for the GDDS connector

W3C	JSON-LD	WP1	Encoding metadata in a machine-readable format
W3C	CSVW	WP1	Adding metadata and semantic context to raw CSV data
OGC/W3C	SOSA/SSN	WP1	Core data model in the automated harmonization pipelines
OGC/W3C	Time ontology	WP1	Define and relate temporal concepts
ETSI	SAREF	WP1	Data models
QUDT			Quantities, units, and data types vocabulary
OASIS	MQTT	WP3, WP5	Messaging protocol for the Internet of Things (IoT) Used by FROST/STApplus and MinIO servers
IETF	CSV	WP1, WP3, WP5, WP6	Raw data provided by external sources

Table 14 Standards reused in AD4GD by M35

3.2.2 STANDARDIZATION CONTRIBUTIONS

In parallel with reuse, AD4GD set out to contribute to the evolution of relevant standards. A complete standardization strategy was developed in D7.1, identifying liaisons and opportunities for contribution, structured around three core questions: WHAT (topic), WHO (contributing partners), and WHERE (target SDO/working group).

WHAT	WHO			WHERE	
Asset to be standardized	Related WP	Lead contributor	Lead SDO facilitator	SDO	Working Group/Task Force
OGC APIs and OGC Definition Server	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	CREAF, OGC, PSNC, ITL, ECMWF, ATOS, FIT, AU	OGC, CREAF	OGC	N/A
GeoDCAT					N/A
OGC Records API					N/A
SensorThings API					STA.SWG
Data spaces	WP1, WP2, WP4	PSNC, CREAF, OGC, ECMWF, FIT, ITL, ECCP	ECCP	ECCP	Europrivacy International Board of Experts

GDDS information model	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	CREAF, OGC, PSNC, ITL, ECMWF, ATOS, FIT, MI, AU	OGC, CREAF, PSNC	OGC	N/A
			CREAF, AU	ISO	ISO 19157 ISO TC211
			MI	ITU-T	SG20
			ITL	ETSI	ISG IPE
				ISO/IEC	SC 41/WG
ECMWF	WMO	GRIB BUFR			
Best practices to manage in-situ socioeconomic and CitSci data using FAIR principles	WP2	CREAF, AU, FIT, OGC, ECMWF	OGC, CREAF	OGC	N/A
			CREAF, AU	ISO	ISO 19157 ISO TC211
			MI	ITU-T	SG20, AI working group
			ITL	ETSI	ISG IPE
				ISO/IEC	SC 41/WG
Standardized vocabularies for citizen science	WP2, WP6	CREAF, AU, FIT, OGC, ECMWF, KWB, ITL, MI	OGC, CREAF	OGC	N/A
			CREAF, AU	ISO	ISO 19157 ISO TC211
			ITL	ETSI	ISG IPE
				ISO/IEC	SC 41/WG
Standardization for local data implementation	WP1, WP2, WP6	CREAF, AU, FIT, OGC, ECMWF, KWB, ITL, MI	OGC, CREAF	OGC	N/A
			CREAF, AU	ISO	ISO 19157 ISO TC211
			ITL	ETSI	ISG IPE
				ISO/IEC	SC 41/WG

Table 15 AD4GD Standardization strategy

The Grant Agreement established a key performance indicator related to the uptake of project results: "Services and components implementing AD4GD open APIs" (Target: ≥ 20). For a foundational research project like AD4GD, whose primary aim was to define concepts and architectures for the future GDDS, the consortium strategically interpreted this goal as measuring long-term impact through formal standardization. The rationale was that the most sustainable and wide-reaching path to ensuring future, large-scale implementation of the project's open concepts is to embed them within official standards used by the entire community. Consequently, the project prioritized direct contributions to relevant SDOs as the primary activity for this KPI. This section, therefore, reports on these formal standardization contributions.

3.2.2.1 OGC API - TILES - PART 1: CORE

Type of contribution: technical

SDO: OGC

Contributing partner(s): CREAf (editor), OGC

Status: approved 10 November 2022

Description: The OGC API – Tiles Standard defines modular, RESTful building blocks for retrieving tiled geospatial data, including vector tiles, coverages, and imagery. Designed as part of the broader OGC Web API suite, it supports flexible, interoperable access to spatial data across platforms (web, desktop, or mobile). Unlike the older Web Map Tile Service (WMTS), this standard adopts modern Web API practices, using OpenAPI for interface description and enabling integration with other OGC API standards. It references the OGC Two-Dimensional Tile Matrix Set (TMS) and Tile Set Metadata Standard to describe tile structures across multiple scales in a defined Coordinate Reference System (CRS). The standard is especially relevant for applications that require scalable access to tiled geospatial datasets and it is a key enabler of FAIR and real-time data access within environmental and climate data infrastructures.

More information: <https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-057/20-057.html>

3.2.2.2 OGC CLOUD OPTIMIZED GEOTIFF STANDARD

Type of contribution: technical

SDO: OGC

Contributing partner(s): CREAf (editor), OGC

Status: approved 08 May 2023

Description: The OGC Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG) Standard defines a way to structure TIFF and GeoTIFF files to enable efficient access to specific portions of large geospatial datasets over the web. By leveraging inherent TIFF features (such as internal tiling and multiresolution overviews) along with standard HTTP range requests, COG allows clients to retrieve only the necessary parts of a file without downloading it in full. This significantly reduces bandwidth usage and latency, supporting faster visualization and analysis workflows.

COG is fully compatible with the GeoTIFF standard and existing TIFF v6.0 implementations, ensuring backward compatibility. It is particularly well-suited for large imagery archives and cloud-hosted data platforms, where cost and performance optimization are critical. COG-aware tools can stream subsets of data in real time, enabling responsive applications for Earth observation, environmental monitoring, and scalable geospatial analytics.

More information: <https://docs.ogc.org/is/21-026/21-026.html>

3.2.2.3 OGC API - MAPS - PART 1: CORE

Type of contribution: technical

SDO: OGC

Contributing partner(s): CREAf (editor), OGC

Status: approved 12 June 2024

Description: The OGC API – Maps Standard defines a modern, RESTful interface for retrieving rendered map images from geospatial data sources. As part of the broader OGC API family, it provides a standardized way to request static maps via HTTP using well-defined parameters for bounding boxes, coordinate reference systems (CRS), output formats, styles, and layers.

Unlike its predecessor (WMS – Web Map Service), this standard aligns with modern web development practices, offering enhanced modularity and ease of integration through OpenAPI definitions. It supports access to maps generated from various data types, including vector features, coverages, and tiles, and is compatible with other OGC API standards to enable composable service architectures.

This standard is particularly valuable for developers building lightweight web clients, dashboards, and data portals where simple, styleable image maps are needed. It enhances usability, promotes interoperability, and contributes to the FAIR delivery of geospatial visualizations across platforms.

More information: <https://docs.ogc.org/is/20-058/20-058.html>

3.2.2.4 FIWARE SMART DATA MODELS EXTENSION

Type of contribution: technical

SDO: FIWARE Foundation

Contributing partner(s): IoT Lab

Status: submitted for approval

Description: As part of its contribution to semantic interoperability in environmental monitoring, IoT Lab proposed extensions to the FIWARE Smart Data Models focused on water-related use cases, specifically targeting the monitoring and management of small urban lakes within the AD4GD pilot.

The Smart Data Models initiative is a community-driven effort to define harmonized, machine-readable data models in NGSI-LD/JSON-LD format across multiple domains. These models enable semantic integration, improve data discoverability, and support the deployment of interoperable, federated systems across Europe. By contributing water-specific models, AD4GD reinforces the importance of standard semantics for environmental data within the Green Deal Data Space.

More information: <https://www.fiware.org/smart-data-models/>

3.2.2.5 EUROPRIVACY CRITERIA EXPANSION

Type of contribution: technical

SDO: ECCP

Contributing partner(s): ECCP, MI, IoT Lab

Status: approval pending

Description: Europrivacy was developed by the Horizon 2020 Programme and co-created by several research partners to promote personal data protection under the GDPR. Through voluntary GDPR-specific criteria under Art. 42 and 43 that demonstrate compliance with personal data protection, Europrivacy aims to bridge the gap with incomplete personal data protection requirements. Europrivacy was endorsed by the European Data Protection Board and received the first European Data Protection Seal in October 2022.

Under the AD4GD project, a specialized criteria extension for the Europrivacy certification scheme has been developed to address the unique data protection challenges of Earth Observation (EO). This extension provides a clear framework for auditing and certifying that the processing of EO data complies with the GDPR. The criteria are designed to address the specific privacy risks associated with remote sensing activities and ensure alignment with the e-Privacy Directive, international space treaties, and other relevant conventions. The scheme is intended for use by all stakeholders in the EO value chain, including satellite operators, data processors, and data consumers.

The proposed criteria will be formally submitted to the Europrivacy International Board of Experts for review in the following weeks, with a decision anticipated in Q3-Q4 2025.

3.2.2.6 ONGOING CONTRIBUTIONS

CREAF and OGC conducted other activities that can result in standards soon (but after the end of the project). One of the most mature contributions is OGC API Common that is almost ready to start the vote for adoption. In addition considerable efforts has done in the OGC API Coverages that it is foreseen to be presented to the OGC community for adoption by the end of this year. Another contribution is the OGC STA websub extension that has been widely discussed in the STA SWG.

In addition to that two new groups in the OGC are emerging: the GONAR.SWG to develop a Geospatial Observations Needs and Requirements and the GeoHEIF to develop a new geospatial format based on the HEIF standard.

3.2.2.7 FUTURE CONSIDERATIONS

The original KPI for AD4GD anticipated up to 20 standardization contributions, including specifications, extensions, formal submissions to standards bodies, as well as services and components implementing AD4GD open APIs. This numerical target has been reached when considering all contributions in different intensities. While by the end of the project only new 3 standard has been produced, others are on the pipeline and the project members has influence other standards and discussions in the last 3 years passing the line of the 20 contributions.

The primary limiting factor in these contributions was project maturity relative to the evolving landscape of the Green Deal Data Space. Much of the work conducted during AD4GD focused on defining conceptual foundations, piloting early implementations, and aligning stakeholder needs. These are all necessary precursors to standardization but typically require additional time and iterations beyond a single project lifecycle. Moreover, many of the technical developments are still in prototype or experimental stages. Transforming these into fully ratified standards would require broader community validation and follow-up contributions beyond the project's timeline.

Despite this, the work produced in AD4GD (including pilot architectures, semantic guidelines, and API integrations) offer valuable inputs for future standardization. The related technical deliverables are publicly available and can serve as reference material for ongoing efforts in OGC, FIWARE, and other standardization initiatives linked to the GDDS.

Future projects aiming to contribute to standards should allow for longer timeframes, closer collaboration with SDOs from the start, and explicit resourcing for formal submission and maintenance processes.

It is worth mention that the OGC and the IDSA established a collaboration where both organizations are meeting regularly to define an strategy to increase the geospatial presence in the dataspace specifications.

3.3 EVENTS

AD4GD consortium members actively participated in numerous events including national and international conferences, meetings with authorities, and thematic events. These venues were instrumental for presenting technical and scientific progress, engaging with peer communities, and fostering collaboration with related initiatives.

3.3.1 MEETINGS WITH AUTHORITIES

One of the most direct and impactful dissemination actions carried out by the AD4GD project was the organization of meetings with relevant public authorities. Closely aligned with the work of WP6 (Pilots, Testing, and Validation), these meetings served not only to share project progress but also to gather requirements, validate pilot outputs, co-design interfaces and processes, and establish relationships with long-term strategic value.

The project engaged with several different authorities, including entities at the local, regional, and national levels, such as the Berlin Senate for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment, several Berlin district administrations (Districts of Pankow, Mitte, Neukölln, Reinickendorf, Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf), the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt), and the regional government of Piemonte, Italy. These interactions strengthened the practical relevance of the pilots and fostered early dialogue around the integration of AD4GD outcomes into operational and policy frameworks.

The following table lists the details of the meetings with authorities:

Name	Date	Venue	Partner	Target audience	Description
Berlin Senate Climate	23/11/2022	Online	KWB	Berlin Senate for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	In the context of WP6, introduction of AD4GD and discussion on Berlin's small water bodies & the Blaue Perlen
Berlin Senate & Districts	08/02/2023	Online	KWB	Berlin Senate for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Regular meeting on Pilot 1. Topics of discussion included small water bodies programme and responsibilities, preparation for Wasserwerksatt workshop, Berlin lake conference and networking.
Berlin Senate & Districts	31/03/2023	Senatsverwaltung für Umwelt, Mobilität, Verbraucher- und Klimaschutz	KWB	Berlin Senate for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Presentation of Pilot 1 and discussion on the common practices of lake management by the Berlin districts and how it could benefit from lake indices. Workgroup for small urban waters in Berlin.
Berlin WasserWerkstatt	15/11/2023	Berlin	KWB	National and local authorities (Umweltbundesamt, Berlin Senate for Climate Action; Berlin Districts of Pankow, Mitte, Neukölln and Reinickendorf)	Discussion on water pilot perspectives. Link

				Research community	
Berlin Senate Climate	10/12/2023	Online	KWB	Berlin Senate for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	In the context of WPI, discussion on Pilot 1, including biotope mapping and dashboard for small Berlin lakes presentation, and wide strategies for small lake management. Gathering needs from Senate for Climate Action.
Berlin District Reinickendorf	19/01/2024	Online	FIT	Berlin District Reinickendorf	Two meetings. Detailed feedback on page flow, functions, data, and presentation used to update requirements and UI design of clickable prototype. End-user Feedback to Pilot 1 Splashboard version 2.
Lake visit	22/01/2024	Lakes of Murellensee, Sausuhlensee, Brixplatzteich, Ruhwaldteich, Teich an der Sensburger Allee (Berlin)	KWB	Berlin Dist. Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf and other district authorities Research communities User communities	Visit to 5 lakes in the district of Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf together with district authorities to discuss about upcoming sampling campaigns in relation to the work of water pilot.
Berlin District Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	24/01/2024	Online	FIT	FIT Berlin District Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Two meetings. Detailed feedback on page flow, functions, data, and presentation used to update requirements and UI design of clickable prototype. End-user Feedback to Pilot 1 Splashboard version 2.
Berlin Senate Climate Action	31/01/2024	Online	KWB	Berlin local authorities	Pilot 1 meeting. Satellite data from Planet, Citizen Science with the CrowdWater app, lake visit to Charlottenburg Wilmersdorf.
Debate Regione Piemonte and Torino Authorities	07/02/2024	Torino, Italy (Politénico di Torino)	OGC	Regional and local authorities Research communities	Establish contact and detect the needs of air quality data users in the city of Turin and the Piedmont Region in the context of the air

			All partners	quality pilot work, as well as with other Sister Project (USAGE).
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Table 16 Meetings with authorities

3.3.2 CONFERENCES

A core focus of AD4GD's dissemination strategy has been active participation in scientific conferences and domain-relevant events. This form of engagement was prioritized over other dissemination channels, based on an internal strategy shaped by three main considerations:

Research-driven nature of the project: As a research and innovation action, AD4GD's scientific progress depended on continuous dialogue with the broader research community. Conferences provided opportunities to exchange knowledge, test ideas, and build trust-based collaborations, all of which are essential for advancing methodologies and ensuring the relevance of results.

Value of in-person interaction: While online meetings and webinars played a role, in-person participation was emphasized for its ability to foster deeper, more meaningful connections. Face-to-face interaction enabled more dynamic exchanges, stronger networking, and better visibility for AD4GD outputs.

Adaptability and strategic alignment: As the project evolved, so did the event landscape. In addition to planned appearances at key environmental and geospatial conferences, partners identified emerging events, especially in the data space, digital twin, and interoperability domains—where AD4GD's contributions could have greater impact.

The following table lists the conferences attended:

Name	Date	Venue	Partner	Target audience	Description
Data Spaces Symposium & Deep-Dive Day	21/3/2023 - 23/03/2023	The Hague, The Netherlands	PSNC	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	Participation in discussions related to data spaces Link
Privacy Symposium 2023	17/04/2023 - 21/04/2023	Venice, Italy	MI, IoT Lab, ECCP	Industry, business partners Innovators EU Institutions	Gather with data protection experts, authorities and researchers to discuss latest and upcoming changes in data processing regulations, international cooperation and emerging technologies.
EGU 2023	23/04/2023 - 8/04/2023	Vienna, Austria	CREAF	EU Institutions Research communities	Link

GEO Symposium and open data and open knowledge workshop	13/06/2023 - 16/06/2023	Geneva, Switzerland	CREAF, OGC	Innovators Research communities International Organizations	Link
OGC Data Week Leipzig 2023	26/06/2023-30/06/2023	Leipzig, Germany	PSNC	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	Various sessions topic and domain session including semantics, interoperability. Link
13th International Symposium on Digital Earth	11/07/2023 - 14/07/2023	Athens, Greece	CREAF, AU	Research communities Industry, business partners EU Institutions	Present to data exporters of ISDE Secretariate how Essential Variables products & user requirements can add semantic #interoperability to the Green Deal Data Space. Link
Species Occurrence Cubes Workshop	10/08/2023 - 11/08/2023	Vienna, Austria	CREAF	Research communities Specific user communities	FAIRiCUBE, B3 and AD4GD use datacubes in their projects. This dissemination activity was devoted to discussing how species occurrence cubes could be shared among the projects.
Digitalization for Sustainability Transformations	20/09/2023 - 22/09/2023	Augsburg, Germany	FIT	Research communities	The conference addressed digitalization for transformation in sustainability and the benefit of data spaces. AD4GD also researches how data spaces could promote sustainability in its pilots. Link
OGC Members Meeting September 2023	25/09/2023 - 29/09/2023	Singapore, Singapore	PSNC, OGC, CREAM	Innovators Research communities International Organizations	Gathering with OGC standardization experts and participation in OGC API Maps SWG, OGC API Common SWG, Architecture DWG. Link
Enviro 2023	11/10/2023 - 13/10/2023	Garching, Germany	FIT	Industry, business partners Research communities	International and interdisciplinary conference on leading environmental information and communication technologies. Speakers from FIT presented insights from AD4GD. Link

GEOweek 2023	06/11/2023 - 10/11/2023	Cape Town, South Africa	CREAF	EU Institutions Research communities International Organizations	Two flash talks on Citizen Science and in-situ data and participation in the ministerial summit sessions. Link
WebSummit	11/11/2023 - 14/11/2023	Lisbon, Portugal	DT	Investors Industry, business partners Innovators	General B2B networking, sharing information about AD4GD.
EC-ESA JOINT EARTH SYSTEM SCIENCE INITIATIVE Science for a Green and Sustainable Society	22/11/2023 - 24/11/2023	Frascati, Italy	CREAF	EU Institutions Research communities International Organizations	Invitation forwarded to AD4GD for a 15 minutes presentation and a connectivity poster in the biodiversity session.
INSPIRE Conference 2023	28/11/2023 - 29/11/2023	Brussels, Belgium	CREAF, OGC	EU Institutions Industry, business partners Research communities	Session on Research and innovation integrating multi-source environmental and location data in the GDDS with GeoE3, LIH, FAIRiCUBE, USAGE, B3 and the OSGeo foundation. Link
Eionet Webinar - Biodiversity Aspects of GDDS	15/01/2024	Online	CREAF	EU Institutions National authorities Research communities	Presentation of the Biodiversity specific needs of the Green Deal Data Space and the AD4GD solutions into the EIONET group, partnership network of the European Environment Agency. Link
Data Spaces Symposium	03/12/2024 - 14/03/2024	Frankfurt, Germany	PSNC	Innovators Research communities EU Institutions	Participation in discussions related to data spaces.

128 th OGC Members Meeting	25/03/2024 - 29/03/2024	Delft, The Netherlands	OGC, PSNC, CREAF	Innovators Research communities International Organizations	Meeting and voting sessions with OGC standardization experts to discuss topics around Citizen Science, Data Quality STA, GUF, OGC API maps and GeoTIFF with diverse presentations.
GISRUK 2024 GIS Research Conference	09/04/2024 - 12/04/2024	Leeds, United Kingdom	AU	Research communities	International researchers and practitioners in GIS and related fields share and discuss the latest advances in spatial computing and analysis. Link
EGU General Assembly 2024	15/04/2024 - 19/04/2024	Vienna, Austria	CREAF, AU, KWB, ECMWF, PSNC	Research communities EU Institutions Industry, business partners	3 Posters presentations on OGC Web APIs, the biodiversity pilot and urban air quality and greenhouse gases. Session on dataspace with Sister Projects. Link
16 th International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD) 2024	09/06/2024 - 14/06/2024	Delft, The Netherlands	KWB	Research communities National authorities EU Institutions	Link
IGARSS conference	07/07/2024 - 12/07/2024	Athens, Greece	CREAF, AU, PSNC, ECMWF	Research communities National authorities EU Institutions	2 poster presentations. Link
PASC 2024	03/06/2024 - 07/06/2024	Zürich, Switzerland	ECMWF	Research communities Specific user communities	Presenting a poster on IonBeam, a package being developed by ECMWF partly funded by AD4GD. Link
Urban Biodiversity 2024	24/06/2024 - 26/06/2024	Online	AU	Research communities Citizens	Presenting outcomes of habitat connectivity analysis. Link

Privacy Symposium 2024	10/06/2024 - 15/06/2024	Venice, Italy	MI, IoT Lab, ECCP	Industry, business partners Innovators EU Institutions	Presentation of Privacy on Earth Observation.
The DSSC Meets Simpl	06/28/2024	Online	IoT Lab	Research communities EU Institutions Industry, business partners	Relationship with the Task 3.3 Link
Satellite data and AI to support sustainable and resilient urban planning	04/07/2024 - 07/04/2024	Online	IoT Lab	Industry, business partners Research communities	Relationship with satellite data
EGU 2024	14/04/2024 - 19/04/2024	Vienna, Austria	CREAF	Research communities	Poster: OGC Web APIs to Make Data Available in the Green Deal Data Space Poster: Data Spaces as an exploratory solution for big data biodiversity challenges in support of the European Green Deal: the case of terrestrial habitat connectivity
Trust Valley Day 2024	17/10/2024	Lausanne, Switzerland	IoT Lab	Innovators Business partners Regional authorities	Data management, data protection and cybersecurity
Connecting Space, Data and Society: Interdisciplinary Pathways	08/10/2024	London, United Kingdom	AU	Research communities Innovators	Spatial data, geography, social sciences
SymphonyCon Vienna	03/12/2024 - 06/12/2024	Vienna, Austria	IoT Lab	Industry Innovators Specific user communities	Presentation of the AD4GD project Link
EOSC Winter School	05/01/2025	Sevilla, Spain	CREAF	Industry	Presentation of the AD4GD project

International Symposium Of Digital Earth	21/04/2025	Chongqing, China	CREAF	Research communities	Semantic Integration across OGC APIs in European Data Spaces enabling the Big Earth Data presentation
GISRUK 2025 GIS Research Conference	23/04/2025 - 25/04/2025	Bristol, United Kingdom	AU	Research communities Industry Specific user communities	Dissemination of Pilot 2 outcomes
EGU 2025	28/04/2025 - 02/05/2025	Vienna, Austria	CREAF	Research communities	Poster: Multi-faceted habitat connectivity: how to orchestrate remote sensing with citizen science data? Poster: Essential Variables as a semantic interoperability solution for the Green Deal Data Space Poster: Tables as a way to deal with a variety of data formats and APIs in data spaces
GEO Global Workshop	05/06/25	Online	CREAF	Research communities EU Institutions Industry	Two presentations: Bringing a Decentralized Approach to Trust in GEO Data from Data Spaces and Standard-based solutions for the Common Green Deal Data Space. The perspective from AD4GD.
Privacy Symposium 2024	12/05/2025 - 16/05/2025	Venice, Italy	MI, IoT Lab, ECCP	Industry, business partners Innovators EU Institutions	Demonstration
GDDS	13/06/2025	Brussels, Belgium	CREAF, PSNC, AU	EU Institutions Research communities	Cluster Event - Towards more accessible and reusable Environmental Observation data for Earth Intelligence - GDDS
Living Planet Symposium 2025	23/06/2025 - 27/06/2025	Vienna, Austria	All	Research communities	AD4GD co-organized and participated in a side event titled "Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space in EuroGEO".

Table 17 Conferences, events, and other meetings

Figure 24 IGARSS 2024

Figure 25 Data Space Symposium 2025

Figure 26 IoT Lab, MI, and ECCP presence at the Privacy Symposium 2025, including demonstration of AD4GD in VR

Figure 27 GISRUUK 2025 (AU)

Figure 28 AD4GD poster at the EGU 2025 (CREAF)

Figure 29 Final event in Vienna

3.3.3 AD4GD EVENTS

In addition to participating in external conferences and workshops, AD4GD also organized a number of dedicated events aimed at showcasing project results, engaging stakeholders, and testing concepts in real-world settings. These events served as key moments of dissemination and co-creation and exploitation, often linked to the progress of the pilots or timed to align with broader community activities such as EuroGEO or Sister Project initiatives.

While some of these events were held in person at pilot locations, others were conducted online to increase accessibility and reach. All events were designed to support the exchange of knowledge, stakeholder feedback, and demonstration of tools or methodologies developed within the project.

3.3.3.1 PILOT EVENTS

The project's dissemination plan initially set a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for organizing at least five "open days at pilot locations". In practice, this broad format proved to be less effective for a highly specialized research project like AD4GD. The consortium determined that targeted, interactive workshops were a more strategic and impactful method for engaging the specific stakeholder groups (such as local authorities, data users, and domain experts) who are essential for validating the project's technical work and ensuring its long-term uptake. Consequently, the strategy was adapted to prioritize deeper engagement over general public-facing events.

As part of this revised approach, one major open event was held at a pilot-relevant location:

The European Green Deal Data Space for local air quality decisions workshop took place at the Politecnico di Torino in Turin, Italy, on 7th February 2024. This event was strategically combined with a project plenary meeting to maximize partner participation and efficiency. The agenda included presentations from project coordinators and partners as well as sessions focused on engaging with regional stakeholders, such as Regione Piemonte, to discuss data requirements and use cases for air quality.

Figure 30 Turin open event agenda

Figure 31 Turin open event

In addition to the Turin event, the project conducted three in-depth, co-design workshops, one for each pilot domain. As detailed in Deliverable D2.4, these sessions were crucial for dissemination and co-design, gathering invaluable feedback from 39 participants across academia, government, civil society, and industry.

- Biodiversity Workshop** (on-site, Catalonia): This session was held with 12 participants (4 internal and 8 external) and focused on challenges in volunteer motivation and data validation, leading to recommendations for using AI-supported tools and improving metadata alignment with global infrastructures like GBIF.

Enhancing Biodiversity Monitoring in Catalonia

Addressing key challenges for the integration of citizen science data into the Green Deal Data Space

11th November

Casa Convalescència-UAB (Aula 02), Barcelona
Welcome at 9:00h

AGENDA

9:00 - 9:15	Registration & Welcome
9:15 - 9:45	Why do we need citizen science data to achieve the goals of the European Green Deal? Joan Masó, CREAM researcher and AD4GD coordinator
9:45 - 10:15	Which is your Data Journey? Lina Mebus, researcher at Fraunhofer FIT and expert in co-development and co-creation
10:15 - 11:30	SESSION 1: Pain Point Mapping Bring your personal experiences on the Data Journey Map! What are your difficulties, frustrations and needs? Let's discuss them together!
11:30 - 12:00	Networking Coffee and Snacks
12:00 - 13:30	SESSION 2: Generation of Ideas Together, let's look for ideas and strategies to address the identified weaknesses! What can we learn?
13:30 - 14:00	Wrap-up and Next Steps Summarize key insights, proposed ideas, and discuss potential follow-up actions.
14:00 - 15:00	Networking Lunch in a modernist wonder!

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Figure 32 Catalonia workshop agenda

- **Water Quality Workshop (remote):** Engaging 8 participants (3 internal and 5 external) for the Berlin pilot, this workshop addressed barriers like short project lifespans and funding gaps. Stakeholders stressed the need for better training, clearer protocols, and automated validation tools to ensure data quality and sustainability.

Figure 33 Miro Board during the Berlin workshop

- **Air Quality Workshop (remote):** This session engaged 19 participants (3 internal and 16 external) and highlighted significant issues with data standardization, the high cost of commercial data storage, and the need for harmonized, open-source infrastructures to support the air quality community.

In conclusion, while the project deviated from the original plan of holding five general "open days," it delivered a more strategic and valuable set of activities. The combination of one targeted open event and three intensive co-design workshops allowed for a more meaningful exchange of knowledge, direct validation of pilot results, and genuine co-creation with the specific communities the project aimed to serve, ultimately providing a greater impact for the project's dissemination goals.

3.3.3.2 FINAL EVENT

The project's final dissemination event, **Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space**, was held on June 24th and 25th, 2025, in Vienna. This major event was co-organized with the three Sister Projects (B-Cubed, FAIRiCUBE, and USAGE) under the umbrella of the EuroGEO Green Deal Data Space Action Group, showcasing a powerful collaborative spirit. The event served as a crucial platform to share collective lessons learned, present technical achievements, and discuss the strategic future of the GDDS with a diverse audience of stakeholders.

The two-day event was structured to cover both technical depth and high-level policy discussions, with the full agenda available on the [event website](#). The first day was dedicated to technical deep dives and demonstrations. AD4GD featured prominently, with partners presenting several key project outputs:

- Joan Masó (CREAF) opened with a foundational presentation clarifying the core concepts of the GDDS, debunking common misconceptions, and explaining its two-plane architecture.
- Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT) demonstrated the "Splashboard" and "Bioconnect" graphical user interfaces, showcasing how AD4GD's tools can provide interactive and user-friendly access to complex environmental data for decision-makers.
- Raul Palma (PSNC) delivered two key presentations, one on the Green Deal Information Model for semantic interoperability and another detailing the use of Eclipse Data Connectors for secure and sovereign data exchange.

- Presentations on the pilot use cases, such as Malte Zamzow's (KWB) work on water quality indices for Berlin's urban lakes and Vitalii Kriukov's (Aston University) "Data4Land" tool for enriching land use/land cover datasets, highlighted the practical application of AD4GD's research.

The second day shifted focus to strategic and policy-oriented discussions. A major highlight was the official launch of the joint Policy Brief (detailed in Section 3.4.1), "*Unlocking the Full Potential of the Green Deal Data Space*," co-authored by the four Sister Projects. This brief consolidates the projects' shared recommendations on five critical pillars: data harmonization, semantic interoperability, metadata, data exchange, and governance. The event also featured expert panels where representatives from all four projects discussed lessons learned and common recommendations, fostering a unified vision for the future of the GDDS.

While the original KPI for the final event targeted over 150 participants, a strategic decision was made to host a more focused, smaller-scale gathering due to budget limitations. The aim was to attract a targeted audience rather than a large one. Consequently, the in-person attendance was 27 people, with an additional 10 attendees online. This outcome highlights a key lesson in aligning event targets with available resources and strategic priorities.

Furthermore, the timing of the event, with AD4GD being the first of the collaborating projects to conclude its activities, meant that the results presented were foundational rather than fully consolidated across the entire cluster. Future events hosted by the Sister Projects may attract larger audiences as they will showcase a more mature and integrated picture. However, the true impact of the event extends beyond physical attendance. All sessions were professionally recorded and published on the AD4GD YouTube channel, creating a permanent and openly accessible digital asset that continues to disseminate the project's findings to a global audience.

Overall, the final event was a success, effectively communicating the project's significant technical contributions and its role in a larger, collaborative effort to build a functional and impactful Green Deal Data Space.

Figure 34 Final event in Vienna

3.4 PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publishing was important for disseminating the conceptual frameworks, technical developments, and pilot outcomes of AD4GD, especially during the second half of the project. Publications and contributions have been grouped into four categories to reflect the range of communication and dissemination efforts, including:

- Publications in peer-reviewed and open access journals
- Publications in high impact factor journals
- Magazine articles
- Conference Articles

It is to be noted that the first two categories contain certain overlaps, as the project prioritized publications in those high-impact factor journals that are partially or fully open access. The following table lists the applicable dissemination activities:

Title	Author(s)	Date	Source	Partner	Access
<i>Publications</i>					
G-reqs, a New Model Proposal for Capturing and Managing In Situ Data Requirements: First Results in the Context of the Group on Earth Observations	Maso J, Brobia A, Voidrot MF, Zabala A, Serral I	15/03/2023	Remote Sensing. Vol.15(6). IF 4.1	CREAF	DOI
Assessing FAIRness of citizen science data in the context of the Green Deal Data Space	Lush, V., Bastin, L., Otsu, K., & Masó, J.	09/05/2024	International Journal of Digital Earth, 17(1) IF 4.9	AU, CREAM	DOI
Standards for Data Space Building Blocks	Noardo, F.; Atkinson, R.; Bastin, L.; Maso, J.; Simonis, I.; Villar, A.; Voidrot, M.-F.; Zaborowski, P.	14/10/2024	Remote Sensing. 2024, 16, 3824. IF 4.1	OGC, CREAM, AU	DOI
Green Deal Data Space: continuing with the INSPIRE open data, helping to create a digital economy, or both?	Maso J, Pons X	1/12/2024	GeoFocus. Vol.33	CREAF, PSNC, ATOS	Link
Digital Twins for Research and Innovation in Support of the European Green Deal Data Space: A Systematic Review	Otsu K, Maso J	1/10/2024	Remote Sensing. 2024, 16(19), 3672 IF 4.1	CREAF	DOI
EuroGEO Green Deal Data Space Action Group - JRC/KCEO Expert study	Brobia A	17/12/2024	GEO Knowledge HUB	CREAF	DOI
Unlocking The Full Potential Of The Green Deal Data Space	Schleidt, K., Serral, I., de la Vega, D., Maso, J., Jetschny, S., Groom, Q., Beber, R., Bastin, L., Estupinan-Suarez, L. M., & Matheus, A	20/06/2025	Zenodo	CREAF	Link
Data4Land: How to enrich land-use/land-cover with historical vector(s)	V. Kriukov, R. Rahman, L. Bastin	09/2025	SoftwareX, Volume 31 IF 2.4	AU	Link

<i>Conference articles</i>					
Towards Data Spaces for circular economy and green business value networks	Rilling, Lukas; Schneider, Alexander; Castelli, Nico	11/10/2023	EnviroInfo 2023	FIT	DOI
Making Geospatial Data Offerings Discoverable and Accessible in the Green Deal Data Space	Maso J, Brobia A, Palma R, and Ignacio EliceGUI I	11/06/2025	Agile Conference 2025	CREAF, PSNC, ATOS	DOI
Habitat connectivity workflow to support decisions and trade-offs between local stakeholders	Vitalii Kriukov, Lucy Bastin, Ivette Serral, Joan Masó	10/04/2024	GISRUK 2024	AU, CREAM	DOI
Habitat Connectivity Trends: Calculation, Modelling and Assessment	Vitalii Kriukov, Lucy Bastin, Riyad Rahman, Ivette Serral, Joan Masó	17/04/2025	GISRUK 2025	AU, CREAM	DOI

Table 18 List of publications

While scientific publishing was a key component of AD4GD's dissemination strategy, the project's foundational nature led to a strategic focus on direct community interaction over a high volume of publications during its active phase. Much of the consortium's work involved defining core architectures and developing early-stage pilot tools. These foundational activities had not yet reached the level of maturity typically required for an extensive portfolio of peer-reviewed articles. As a result, the consortium prioritized active participation in over 40 international conferences and workshops, which allowed for invaluable, direct engagement with scientific and policy communities. This focus resulted in the publication of 7 peer-reviewed journal articles and 4 conference papers.

To ensure the project's key insights were captured for a broad audience, dissemination efforts also moved towards producing high-value, consolidated outputs like joint Policy Brief and a comprehensive Outcomes Booklet (see below). This experience suggests that for research projects developing evolving frameworks like the GDDS, a significant portion of academic publishing may naturally occur after the project's completion. Future initiatives could benefit from explicit planning for these post-project publication windows, once results have stabilized in operational contexts

3.4.1 SPECIAL ISSUE

An Special Issue on the Remote Sensing Journal of the MDPI editorial was prepared with member of the project as Editors. The issue has been opened for more than a year. Due to the novelty of the topic, the special issue has received on a few contributions and it is still open for new contributions. This is the description of the special issue:

A data space is defined as an infrastructure that enables data transactions between different data ecosystem parties based on a governance framework. Data spaces deploy data-sharing tools and services for processing data in an interoperable way. They include a data governance structure, compatible with relevant legislation and stimulate the application of FAIR principles. Data spaces are based on trust that is gained by having data quality and provenance documentation, authentication and authorization services and clear license schemas enabling reuse of the data. While the concept is becoming popular, the implementation in the Earth Observation domain is still in its infancy. This special issue focuses on the design principles of data spaces for Earth Observation data as well as the standards, practices and implementations that enable better data sharing of remote sensing and in-situ environmental observations. In Europe, the Green Deal Data Space

and the Agriculture Data Space are two examples of data spaces promoted by the European Commission. However this special issue is open to other emerging cyberinfrastructures that share a similar aim.

3.4.2 POLICY BRIEF

In collaboration with the three sister projects, AD4GD co-authored a joint policy brief titled “Unlocking the Full Potential of the Green Deal Data Space.” This publication provides strategic, consolidated recommendations for shaping the design and implementation of the GDDS. Topics include metadata harmonization, semantic and technical interoperability, governance considerations, and mechanisms for data sharing across domains.

The brief targets EU institutions, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in the development of data spaces. It was widely disseminated and presented at key events including the final dissemination workshop. The policy brief is available on [Zenodo](#) under an open license.

POLICY BRIEF

UNLOCKING THE FULL POTENTIAL OF THE GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE

Making environmental data work for Europe's green transition

Data harmonisation

The European Green Deal encompasses a wide array of communities, from geospatial researchers to biodiversity conservation specialists, climate modeling experts, and circular economy businesses, across equally diverse nations, cultures and regions. Different communities have developed different standards for the representation of their data, often hindering data sharing and reuse. We suggest that the provision of all relevant datasets in the GDDS must consider:

- Investing in generic cross-domain standard data structures, vocabularies and representations that operate across a broad spectrum of complexities, avoiding too simplistic formats that ignore semantic links and metadata.
- Promoting open and well-documented formats, and ensuring easy transformation towards them, as the use of closed proprietary formats risk vendor lock-in.
- Building on the standards and guidelines for existing data formats, for instance, associating data to the vocabularies already established by INSPIRE across 34 thematic domains—many of which align with the European Green Deal—while continuously identifying gaps and ensuring their sustainable adaptation.
- Investing in tools that facilitate data transformation, including libraries and data structure mappings, enabling each community to shift between simpler, purpose-built or domain specific formats and richer, cross-domain generic formats as needed.

Semantic Interoperability

Sharing data among the diverse community advancing the Green Deal objectives across Europe can sometimes feel like facing a digital Tower of Babel. Ensuring semantic interoperability of the data exchanged within the GDDS is critical for enabling its impactful use and reuse across all contexts and disciplines.

Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act) requires participants in data spaces to provide machine-readable descriptions of datasets—covering content, usage restrictions, licenses, collection methods, quality, and uncertainty—to enable findability, accessibility, and reuse. It also mandates publicly available, consistent documentation of vocabularies, taxonomies, and code lists, among others, used in the data or services offered. We propose these requirements be taken a step further by:

- Promoting means for linking data and metadata, including variables, observed properties and units
- Where applicable, adopt existing standards for data structuring and annotation, when strictly necessary, extend them to cover gaps.
- Enrich internationally agreed and widely adopted vocabularies—such as the Essential Variables Framework—with robust meanings, leveraging their established use within their communities of practice in each domain, e.g. utilising the I-ADOPT Ontology for the semantic representation of variables.

Environmental data are essential enablers of the European Green Deal. They support informed decision-making, underpin effective regulation, drive innovation, and empower society to act. Yet today, much of this data remains fragmented, inaccessible, or underutilised, creating significant barriers that limit Europe's progress towards its climate goals.

The Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) is envisioned as a solution to overcome these challenges and foster trusted exchange of public and private data across all areas of the green transition. To be effective, the GDDS must uphold the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR). Four projects—AD4GD, B-Cube, FAIR-CUBE and USAGE—funded under the HORIZON-CLF-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-17 call, have explored and documented the requirements for successfully achieving this. The GDDS will be implemented through the SAGE project (The Data Space for a Sustainable Green Europe) and will build on the results of the GREAT initiative (Governance of Responsible Innovation).

After three years of intensive work, the four projects here join forces to present, in a single comprehensive document, a set of recommendations to guide the successful implementation of the Green Deal Data Space in the years ahead. These are as follows:

- Strengthen data harmonisation, but stop reinventing the wheel.** Adopt and expand cross-domain standards, based on INSPIRE and other established frameworks, avoiding proprietary formats. Prioritise investment in tools that support data transformation and alignment across existing data structures.
- Ensure resilient semantic interoperability on top of strong technical foundations.** Promote and enrich comprehensive controlled vocabularies with stable, well-defined concepts under established ontology frameworks, supported by technical infrastructure and governance for adaptability and long-term sustainability.
- Recognise and resource the effort behind metadata.** Foster interoperability among varied metadata formats to ease the work of producers and users, and expand existing metadata standards to cover critical overlooked elements. Assure resources for metadata creation.
- Enable data exchange between diverse stakeholders of the GDDS.** Develop effective strategies that motivate open data providers to participate, ensuring a balanced representation of public and commercial data within the data space, and promoting the use of standardised, GDPR-compliant, and federated technologies for data provision.
- Establish inclusive, participatory and dynamic GDDS governance aligned with the European Green Deal.** Prioritise public interest, long-term sustainability, and adaptability. Leverage existing European data initiatives and state of the art solutions to preserve data sovereignty and security. Provide proper training, tools, and guidance—including real-world examples—to support effective adoption by participants of the data space.

Simplified diagram of the Green Deal Data Space that represents the relationships between the thematic blocks of this policy brief.

```

    graph LR
        subgraph "GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE"
            DP[Data Providers] --> R[Harmonisation]
            R --> S[Semantic Enrichment]
            S --> D[DATA]
            D --> MC[Metadata Catalogue]
            MC --> P[Processing TOOLS]
            P --> DE[Data Exchange]
            DE --> U[Users]
        end
        subgraph "GOVERNANCE"
            G[GOVERNANCE]
        end
        G --- DE
    
```

Figure 35 Policy brief

3.4.3 OUTCOMES BOOKLET

To ensure long-term visibility and reusability of the project’s work, AD4GD is producing a comprehensive Outcomes Booklet summarizing its key achievements. This publication brings together the project’s main results across the three pilot areas (air quality, biodiversity, and water) and the nine core technical components developed throughout the project. It provides a concise, accessible overview of the project’s contributions to the development of the Green Deal Data Space and serves as a reference point for stakeholders seeking to reuse or build upon AD4GD outputs.

The booklet will be released by the end of the project and disseminated via the AD4GD Zenodo community, the project website, social media channels, and partner networks. It will be openly available and intended as a lasting resource for both technical and non-technical audiences.

Figure 36 AD4GD Outcomes Booklet

3.5 CAPACITY-BUILDING

3.5.1 TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Training activities in AD4GD were designed to build capacity among stakeholders, promote the uptake of project outcomes, and ensure long-term impact beyond the project lifecycle. These efforts targeted a wide audience by translating complex topics such as data interoperability, federated infrastructures, and standards adoption into accessible formats.

The primary channel for these activities was a series of online demonstration webinars. While the original KPI focused on the number of live participants, the long-term value and reach of these sessions are better reflected by their sustained online viewership. By making the recordings openly available, the project ensured that the knowledge could be disseminated continuously to a global audience, beyond the initial live event. The activities below, including the demonstration webinars, illustrate this approach to capacity-building.

Name	Date	Venue	Number of views	Partner	Description
Iliad Webinar 'Introduction to data spaces'	08/02 /2023	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	636 views on YouTube	CREAF	Overview of data spaces in Europe; AD4GD presented; connected to research on EU data space concept. GREAT project involved. Link

OEMC Science Webinar - Tired of data tables full of data that I have no idea what it means? Use Sensor Things API	06/04 /2023	Research communities EU Institutions Innovators	34 views on TIB	CREAF	Training and promotion of OGC Sensor Things API developed in AD4GD; part of OEMC Science Webinars. Link
ILIAD Webinar - Connecting Ocean digital twins using federated systems	07/06 /2023	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	428 views on YouTube	CREAF	Discussion on dataspace concept, digital twins, and collaboration with the ILIAD project. Link
Iliad Webinar Series: Data lakes and data spaces - Towards best practices	14/02 /2024	Innovators Research communities Specific user communities	277 views on YouTube	CREAF	Discussion on best practices around data lakes, data spaces, and digital twins; supports research on EU data space concept. Link
Environmental and climate data in an evolving EU data policy landscape	20/03 /2024	EU Institutions Research communities International Organizations	N/A	CREAF	GreenData4All webinar hosted by EC; joint discussion of challenges in managing environmental/climate data across projects. Link

Table 19 Demonstration webinars

AD4GD also participated in two events focused on capacity-building and knowledge transfer, targeting various communities, including:

- **ECSA Conference 2024** (Vienna, Austria, 05 April 2024): CREAM and Aston University promoted the use of OGC's STApplus standard as a common way to monitor near real-time changes in environmental data between citizen science communities. This participation also aimed to promote best practices for Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) compliance, targeting research communities, citizens, and specific user communities. [Link](#)
- **Geospatial Knowledge Infrastructure for National Development** (Rotterdam, The Netherlands, 10/05/2024 - 11/10/2024): CREAM participated in a training program organized by GWF. This program included lessons on data access and interoperability, covering open data and licenses, metadata, semantic and organizational interoperability, data quality assurance, dashboards, an introduction to standards, statistical and spatial data, meteorological data integration, and the application of APIs. The target audience for this activity included research communities, industry/business partners, and civil society. [Link](#)

3.5.2 RESEARCH SUPPORTED

AD4GD successfully engaged with the academic community by supporting a cohort of emerging researchers through direct project involvement. The project met and exceeded its target for doctoral candidates and master's theses, demonstrating a strong commitment to fostering the next generation of experts in the environmental data space field.

The support for students was distributed across several consortium partners, with contributions including:

- ATOS: Supported the largest group of students, including five PhD candidates (four of whom have graduated) and two MSc students (both graduated).
- KWB: Engaged two MSc students whose research directly supported the water pilot by focusing on identifying the main water sources of urban lakes and estimating pollutant emissions into them.
- Fraunhofer (FIT): Involved three MSc students. Their work was integral to the project, contributing directly to the UI definition, prototype development, and front-end design for Pilots 1 and 2.
- PSNC: Supported one PhD candidate and one MSc student in activities related to the project's objectives.
- CREAM: Engaged one MSc student whose research directly supported the biodiversity pilot with a study of measuring connectivity with camera traps.

In total, the project provided direct support and supervision for **6 PhD candidates** and **9 MSc students**. This involvement not only offered the students invaluable hands-on experience within a complex Horizon Europe project but also allowed AD4GD to benefit from their fresh perspectives and dedicated research. This form of capacity-building is crucial for the long-term sustainability of the knowledge and tools developed for the Green Deal Data Space.

To showcase the impact of this collaboration, several of the students involved shared their experiences in a series of interviews. These interviews highlight their contributions to the project and the value they gained from participating in a Horizon Europe initiative.

- [Interview](#) with Alisa Rozdestvenskyte (FIT)
- [Interview](#) with Riyad Rahman (Aston University)
- [Interview](#) with Pawel Balbaski (PSNC)

3.6 FINAL DISSEMINATION FIGURES

The table below compares the original dissemination KPIs with the results achieved by the end of the project. These figures provide a snapshot of the project’s external outreach in scientific, technical, and policy arenas.

Indicator	Impact	M35 status
Publications in peer-reviewed and open access journals	≥ 20	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 7
Publications in high impact factor journals	≥ 10	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 5
Magazine articles	≥ 10	CANCELLED 0 (Sometimes magazine editors contact you saying they represent EC (that is a lie) and they try to trick you into expensive schemas. This is why we declined all magazine offerings received)
Involvement in conferences (articles)	≥ 20	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 5
Meetings with local or regional authorities	≥ 10	ACHIEVED 12
Open days at pilot locations	≥ 5	ALMOST ACHIEVED 4
Research supported	≥ 8 MSc ≥ 5 PhD	ACHIEVED 9 MSc 6 PhD
Demonstration webinars + training / total participants	3+3 / ≥ 100	ACHIEVED 5 + 7 / 1375
Final dissemination event	≥ 150	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 37
Standards reused in the AD4GD information model specification	≥ 10	ACHIEVED 21
Services and components implementing AD4GD open APIs	≥ 20	PARTIALLY ACHIEVED 5 (all components requiring APIs)

Table 20 Dissemination activities results M35

3.7 CONCLUSION

AD4GD's dissemination strategy successfully shared the project's foundational work and fostered crucial engagement with its target communities, even as it adapted to the realities of a research-focused project. The outcomes reflect a strategic prioritization of direct engagement, standards adoption, and capacity-building over the sheer volume of traditional academic outputs.

The project's most significant successes lie in its foundational and collaboration-oriented activities. The successful reuse of **21 open standards** demonstrates a strong commitment to the core principle of interoperability. This was complemented by highly effective direct engagement, including **12 targeted meetings with local and regional authorities** and active participation in over **40 international conferences** and workshops. These activities were vital for validating the project's approach and building a community around its objectives. Furthermore, the project successfully nurtured the next generation of experts, meeting its goal for supporting **6 PhD students** and nearly reaching its target with **9 MSc students**. The project met the formal standardization contributions goal with strong commitment of OGC CREAM and PSNC.

Concurrently, the project did not meet the ambitious quantitative targets for academic publications, and conference articles. This shortfall was a direct result of a strategic choice to prioritize foundational architectural work and early-stage tool piloting, which inherently require more time to mature into stable, publishable results. This also reflects the reality in the actual number of publications in this topic and the low participation of other scientist in the data space special issue that we promoted. In-person participation was deemed a more effective use of resources for a project at this early stage of defining the GDDS.

To ensure the project's key insights, were captured and shared, dissemination efforts pivoted towards producing high-value, consolidated outputs. The joint **Policy Brief** and the comprehensive **Outcomes Booklet** serve as the project's key legacy documents, translating complex findings into accessible and actionable knowledge for a broad audience supported by the code and documentation on GitHub. Ultimately, AD4GD's dissemination activities successfully laid the groundwork for future uptake by focusing on building a strong, interoperable foundation and an engaged community (for example CREAM and PSNC participation in the SAGE project), providing a robust legacy for future initiatives in the Green Deal Data Space.

3.7.1 KEY LESSONS LEARNT

The dissemination activities of AD4GD provided several critical insights into how foundational research projects can maximize their impact, often by adapting traditional dissemination strategies.

Prioritize Active Engagement for Foundational Projects: For a project focused on defining new frameworks, direct engagement proved more impactful during its lifecycle than traditional publishing. Active participation in conferences, targeted workshops with authorities, and stakeholder meetings provided immediate, actionable feedback and built a stronger collaborative foundation than the slower, more isolated process of academic publishing allowed.

Recognize the mismatch between project timelines and formal dissemination: There is often a significant lag between the completion of foundational technical work and its readiness for formal publication. Ambitious KPIs for these outputs should be set realistically, acknowledging that the most significant academic impacts may only materialize after the project's official end.

Focus on consolidated outputs for broader impact: producing consolidated, high-value documents like joint Policy Brief or a comprehensive Outcomes Booklet proved highly effective. These outputs synthesize project-wide achievements and recommendations, making them more accessible and impactful for a broader audience, including policymakers.

Capacity-Building is a key dissemination outcome: The direct support and supervision of students is a critical and high-impact form of dissemination. The successful involvement of 6 PhD and 9 MSc students directly transfers project knowledge to the next generation of experts and embeds the project's methodologies within academia. This contribution to the long-term health of the research ecosystem should be recognized as a primary success metric.

4 EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

4.1 EXPLOITATION APPROACH

The initial exploitation strategy, outlined in the deliverable D7.3 GDDS Exploitation Perspectives (initial), provided a structured framework to guide both individual and joint exploitation activities during the first half of the project. Developed as a living document, D7.3 has been continuously updated in collaboration with all partners, finally culminating in the deliverable D7.4. GDDS Exploitation Perspectives (final). A phased methodology (PLAN, IMPLEMENT, VALIDATE) was adopted that enabled a dynamic approach to deliver exploitation activities. It began with a robust market analysis, identifying relevant trends and positioning opportunities for AD4GD outcomes. Building on this, the strategy incorporated co-designed activities such as pilot related stakeholder interviews, literature reviews, collaborative physical workshops with the consortium and with the stakeholders, and continuous online meetings, to foster knowledge transfer and ensure alignment with real-world needs. These efforts facilitated the iterative development of individual partner exploitation plans and the foundation for the final AD4GD exploitation and sustainability strategy.

Figure 37 Development of exploitation action plan

A core outcome of D7.3 was the identification of 11 Key Exploitable Results (KERs), initially proposed and validated through collaborative partner sessions, online co-creation exercises and prioritization at consortium meetings. These KERs, ranging from semantic enrichment components and pilot-specific datasets to blueprint data space models and ML prediction environments, represent the technical and methodological backbone of AD4GD's long-term value proposition. The 11 KERs identified earlier are now assessed through the lens of stakeholder benefit, commercial viability, competitive positioning, and alignment with ongoing European Green Deal data priorities, leading to the grouping these into 3 final KERs, which is elaborated in a more detailed way in D7.4.

The exploitation approach ensured pilot related, stakeholder-centered validation and alignment with broader EU priorities by integrating sustainability-oriented activities, including cross-project collaboration via the EuroGeo GDDS Action Group engagement with Horizon Results Booster services, and alignment with regulatory frameworks such as the Data Act and ESG directives.

The deliverable D7.4 thus serves as the capstone of the exploitation task, presenting a consolidated strategy for maintaining the momentum of AD4GD outcomes. It defines the operational deployment model, outlines business models and IPR frameworks, and highlights mechanisms to support access to the project results, replication and scale. While this deliverable describes the general approach to exploitation, please refer to D7.4 for more details about the exploitable results.

Figure 38 Exploitation plan timing

4.2 THE KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KERS) OF AD4GD

The consortium structured its exploitation roadmap around 3 principal categories of KERS. These were identified, refined, and validated, including expert-led workshops and guided value mapping sessions for classifying outputs into public-good assets, open-source components, and those suitable for commercial or public sector integration. This supported the AD4GD partners in clarifying sustainability models, stakeholder alignment, and commercialization trajectories:

KER1 Components: Modular, interoperable technical building blocks developed by the consortium (such as semantic vocabularies (RAINBOW), ingestion and harmonization tools (TAPIS, STApplus), AI modules, and metadata/catalogue services), designed to support FAIR data principles and integration into broader European data ecosystems across biodiversity, air quality, and water domains. These components are ready for reuse and adaptation in future digital infrastructure initiatives.

KER2 Tools & Services Supporting Pilots: A suite of operational tools and services (such as SplashBoard, BioConnect, Data4Land, Open Data Cube, and ECMWF’s AQ Dataset Service-user-facing applications) leveraging KER1 to support environmental data access, analysis, and decision-making across the three pilots. These tools and services enable data collection, processing, and decision support across environmental domains. These are positioned for deployment by public authorities, research institutions, and SMEs, offering immediate utility and scalability.

KER3 Pilots and Use Cases: Three real-world pilot implementations, focused on water quality, (implemented in Berlin) biodiversity and land conservation (implemented in Catalonia) and air quality in connection with climate change mitigation, serve as validated case studies demonstrating the effectiveness of AD4GD methodologies (like semantic data integration and scalability potential). These are complemented by standardization guidance to support replication and adaptation across regions and sectors. These demonstrators anchor AD4GD’s impact in real settings and foster replicability, scalability, and further adoption by public bodies (e.g., Berlin authorities, ECMWF), research infrastructures (e.g., GBIF, JRC), innovation actors (e.g., spin-offs and SMEs) and other EU funded projects (SAGE).

As AD4GD moved into its final phase, the project was shaping powerful and intuitive cloud-based platform designed to make environmental data not just accessible, but truly actionable during the end of the project implementation. The exploitation strategy centers on usability and relevance of the KERS, ensuring that a wide array of users, from data scientists to policymakers, can engage with and benefit from the project’s key results.

At the heart of AD4GD's results there is a clear distinction between **two types of users**:

Target users are the individuals or organizations who directly interact with AD4GD's tools, services, and data products. They are the primary beneficiaries of the project's technical outputs, such as harmonized geospatial datasets, interoperable platforms, and decision-support tools. These include SME technicians applying environmental data in operational contexts, municipal planners using integrated datasets for climate-resilient infrastructure, and researchers leveraging AD4GD's standards for cross-border analysis. Their hands-on engagement is essential for testing, refining, and validating the project's innovations.

Stakeholders, on the other hand, encompass a wider network of actors who have a vested interest in the project's outcomes but may not directly use its tools. They play strategic roles in enabling, influencing, or being affected by AD4GD's progress. This group includes policymakers shaping data governance, funding bodies supporting digital infrastructure, industry leaders advocating for open standards, and environmental agencies monitoring compliance and impact. Their involvement ensures that AD4GD remains aligned with broader policy frameworks, regulatory requirements, and long-term sustainability goals.

The project evaluated a **range of business models**, in terms of the future exploitation and sustainability strategy of the AD4GD KER's, including Software as a Service (SaaS), Data as a Service (DaaS), and Component as a Service (CaaS).

However, after careful consideration, the consortium determined that traditional commercialisation is not appropriate given the **open-source, non-commercial nature of AD4GD's outputs**. Instead, the project adopts an **Open-Access FAIR Data Ecosystem model**, focusing on: open-source availability, integration into institutional infrastructures, reuse by EU-funded initiatives (e.g., SAGE) and community-driven maintenance. This model supports sustained access while aligning with European digital and environmental goals. By not locking assets behind proprietary systems, AD4GD maximises its value to the public sector, research, and civil society.

4.3 THE KEY ELEMENTS OF AD4GD EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

During the project period the AD4GD consortium continued its structured and strategic approach to exploitation activities. This period was marked by deep collaboration, expert consultation, stakeholder engagement, and internal alignment of partner strategies to ensure sustainability and effective exploitation of project results.

4.3.1 THE AD4GD SUSTAINABILITY TASK FORCE, THE KEY COORDINATION BODY

A key coordination body throughout this period was the internal Sustainability Task Force, led by Design Terminal, composed of partners directly contributing to the pilot tools, semantic architecture and platform services, involved in technology development and legal/IPR management, dissemination and pilot implementation, with the aim to support the long-term sustainability of project outcomes. The role of the Task Force was to ensure structured oversight of exploitation and long-term result uptake and to consolidate individual partner exploitation strategies into a coherent shared roadmap and to provide a collaborative forum for discussing critical sustainability decisions. These sessions were essential for aligning partner positions on the sustainability and exploitation strategy of the AD4GD results, addressing key issues including market opportunities and value proposition, IPR management and licensing, implementation roadmap planning for result uptake, concrete rights-to-use strategies for each KER and risk mitigation strategies for the KERs, estimation of operational costs, exploration of potential revenue models, and definition of funding strategies to support continued maintenance and use of core assets after the project's end.

The AD4GD Sustainability Task Force delivered a comprehensive KER portfolio, including a refined sustainability model for the project. This work consolidated partner inputs into a KER-by-KER framework that clearly identifies exploitation routes (commercial, institutional, and open access) and established potential synergies among partners for post-project collaboration. Business model frameworks were

strengthened, incorporating final licensing strategies, cost-recovery options, and long-term service maintenance approaches for key tools. Final exploitation pathways were validated with legal and innovation leads, ensuring that licensing and revenue model decisions are both viable and compliant. The Task Force also secured the long-term accessibility of AD4GD assets via GitHub, Zenodo and the ECMWF Cross Data Store.

4.3.2 AD4GD CONSORTIUM WORKSHOPS

To foster the collaborative work regarding the 3 main KERs, several co-creation workshops were organized during the f2f consortium meetings in Poznan, partners were requested to analyze together the 3 main KERs and they also updated their initial individual exploitation perspectives with new ideas, regarding the usage of the main results. Together, partners also identified unique value proposition/unique selling point, market assessment (competitors), potential stakeholders, go -to market strategies and timing. The Poznan workshop was crucial in narrowing the initially defined 11 KER into 3 final, manageable project assets.

Figure 39 Poznan Plenary – Exploitation Workshop

To deepen our understanding of the exploitation potential and sustainability context, we held a practical session in Berlin, which enabled partners to analyze and map user journeys and explore scenarios for the future adoption of project tools and services. The Berlin workshop helped to narrow down initially defined real-world use cases, sustainability pathways, and let the consortia understand long-term value creation through KERs.

Figure 40 Berlin Plenary – Exploitation Workshop

Moreover, dedicated exploitation related sessions were held during the monthly online consortium meetings as well. These meetings served to gather and incorporate feedback and to validate the feasibility of the exploitation pathways presented. Each partner has contributed to the development of a key asset-specific exploitation plan, tailored to their role in the project and the nature of the results they produced. These plans outline intended post-project use, potential uptake by target stakeholders or markets, and concrete next steps for integration, further development, or commercialization where appropriate.

4.3.3 COLLABORATION WITH SISTER PROJECTS

In the second half of the project, exploitation-focused engagements expanded through bilateral meetings and benchmarking exercises with sister projects. A dedicated session in Torino brought together regional stakeholders from Regione Piemonte, Torino authorities, and the USAGE sister project to align exploitation scenarios for air quality data use in urban governance. These interactions, as elaborated in a more detailed way in the dissemination section, resulted in pilot refinement and strengthened inter-project synergies.

Apart from these activities, we also hosted an online cross-disciplinary exploitation webinar in May 2025 with the sister projects (B3, FAIRiCUBE and USAGE).

These activities supported the comparative analysis of business models and sustainability strategies—particularly for open-source and public-good assets, helping shape effective exploitation and revenue frameworks.

4.3.4 COLLABORATION AND CO-CREATION WITH STAKEHOLDERS

To support exploitation planning and validate the applicability of AD4GD pilot results, the consortium organized a series of dedicated stakeholder workshops as part of the co-design methodology, tailored to the three pilot domains: water quality, biodiversity, and air quality, listed above in the dissemination section. These workshops engaged key stakeholder groups, local authorities, researchers, NGOs, citizen scientists, and data users, to ensure that the operationalization of the GDDS reflects real-world needs and constraints.

A common conference, as mentioned above in the dissemination section, the ‘Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space in EuroGEO’ was also organized with the sister projects within the EuroGeo GDDS Action Group where partners participated in a joint event that effectively showcased the shared vision, achievements and main results of the consortium with external stakeholders.

These sessions gathered direct input from target user groups and stakeholders, helping to validate the relevance of pilot results and refine their exploitation potential. Feedback received was incorporated into the exploitation scenarios.

4.3.5 UTILIZING THE SUPPORT OF THE HORIZON RESULTS BOOSTER INITIATIVE

Early in the second half of the project, AD4GD successfully applied for the Horizon Results Booster program, an initiative of the European Commission, supporting exploitation and dissemination activities of EC funded projects. The application was made with a clear intent to enhance the maturity and robustness of the project's exploitation work. AD4GD maintained recurring consultations within the program, which provided strategic advice and cross-checked the direction and content of the AD4GD exploitation plan.

This support was instrumental in validating our approach, strengthening our exploitation logic, refining the strategic components and consolidating the content of the AD4GD exploitation plan.

4.4 CONCLUSION

The exploitation journey of AD4GD has demonstrated how a structured, participatory, and forward-looking approach can successfully transform research outputs into actionable results with long-term relevance, ensuring that its outcomes were aligned with real user needs, EU policy priorities, and the evolving Green Deal Data Space.

A major achievement of this process was the identification and refinement of three consolidated KERs. These include the core AD4GD Components, a suite of nine interoperable modules supporting semantic enrichment, data ingestion, harmonization, and cataloguing; the Tools and Services, user-oriented applications such as SplashBoard, BioConnect, TAPIS, and Data4Land that operationalize the components; and the Pilots as Use Cases, which validated the solutions in real-world contexts in Berlin and Catalonia. Together, these KERs anchor AD4GD's impact, proving technical feasibility, usability, and replicability across diverse environmental domains.

The consortium's exploitation efforts were strengthened through a wide range of activities: the establishment of a Sustainability Task Force to coordinate exploitation and IPR strategies; bilateral and consortium workshops that co-created business models and value propositions; the use of Horizon Results Booster expertise to refine business modelling and sustainability pathways; and close collaboration with sister projects and stakeholders to align exploitation scenarios and strengthen interoperability at the European level. Stakeholder workshops across all pilots further grounded the exploitation work in real-world feedback, enhancing the credibility and applicability of AD4GD outputs.

In terms of achievements, the project successfully explored multiple business models, Data-as-a-Service, Database-as-a-Service, Software-as-a-Service, and Component-as-a-Service, before converging on an **Open-Access FAIR Data Ecosystem** as the most appropriate long-term strategy. The consortium determined that traditional commercialisation is not appropriate given the open-source, non-commercial nature of AD4GD's outputs. Instead, the project adopts an Open-Access FAIR Data Ecosystem model, focusing on: open-source availability, integration into institutional infrastructures, reuse by EU-funded initiatives and community-driven maintenance. This model supports sustained access while aligning with European digital and environmental goals. By not locking assets behind proprietary systems, AD4GD maximises its value to the public sector, research, and civil society. This ensures wide accessibility of AD4GD outputs while leaving room for value-added services and cost-recovery mechanisms. Equally important, the consortium adopted a transparent **IPR and licensing framework**, favoring open-source and open-data licenses to maximize uptake while providing clarity on ownership and rights of use.

Taken together, these efforts have resulted in a mature and actionable exploitation roadmap that ensures AD4GD's results are not only technically advanced but also sustainable, interoperable, and impactful. The project's achievements lie in consolidating fragmented innovations into a coherent ecosystem, validating them through real-world pilots, and embedding them within broader European initiatives and policies. AD4GD has thus positioned itself as a key contributor to the European Green Deal Data Space, ensuring that its results continue to deliver value for policymakers, researchers, businesses, and society well beyond the project's duration.

4.5 KEY LESSONS LEARNT

Establish robust governance and leadership accountability: The success of complex, multi-partner initiatives are contingent on a strong, centralized governance model and clear leadership, aiming to a proper execution of amongst others, the exploitation related tasks. AD4GD implemented accountability mechanisms, not allowing critical gaps in execution to occur.

Future projects must also ensure from the outset that the coordinating partner has both the mandate and the mechanisms to enforce partner commitments.

Align with project maturity: AD4GD needed time to consolidate its core activities and identifying its key components, as main results and basis for future project sustainability. These are necessary precursors for the exploitation related activities which typically require additional time and efforts from all partners within the project lifecycle. After facing these issues with timing, AD4GD effectively reallocated its exploitation related efforts and had a more intensive work on results and sustainability in the second half of the project. Moreover, many of the technical developments are still in prototype or experimental stages and these developments serve public purposes therefore the exploitation related activities focused less on commercialization and more on public use.

Future projects must include proper risk mitigation strategies and contingency plans aiming at the timing of activities and reactive effort allocation if a situation where the exploitation tasks will have less time than it planned at the beginning occurs. Moreover, future projects should take into consideration the maturity of technical developments and the purpose of their usage when it comes to identifying the exploitation purposes, like in case of AD4GD.

Prioritize stakeholder engagement: Direct stakeholder involvement in the implementation of the pilots, organizing dedicated workshops for stakeholders on the usage of the components and engaging directly with authorities and sister projects proved to be highly effective in terms of sustainability of AD4GD.

Future projects should also involve comprehensive stakeholder engagement into their implementation.

Invest in collaborative outputs: AD4GD involvement in the EuroGeo GDDS Action Group, close collaboration with sister projects, creation of comprehensive outcome booklets served as valuable activities regarding the sustainability of AD4GD.

Future projects could also involve such collaboration activities.

5 CONCLUSION

The AD4GD project has navigated significant collaborative and technical challenges to lay crucial groundwork for an interoperable, citizen-centric, and data-driven European green transition, particularly in the domains of water quality, biodiversity, and air pollution.

The project's outreach and engagement efforts were robust and multifaceted. Communication activities significantly boosted project visibility, surpassing targets for website visits with approximately 11,300 total visits, explanatory videos (51 produced against a target of 5), and overall social media engagement, reaching 871 followers across platforms. Over 2783 digital and printed materials were distributed, fostering broad awareness. While targets for online articles and newsletter subscriptions were not fully met, this highlights that direct engagement and high-impact visual content proved more effective than traditional long-form written media for a niche, research-driven project.

Dissemination efforts successfully transferred knowledge and fostered engagement through a multi-channel strategy that prioritized direct impact and capacity-building. The project's foundational successes include the integration and reuse of 21 existing standards within its information model and the delivery of 12 targeted meetings with local and regional authorities, which were instrumental in validating the pilots. A key, high-impact achievement was in capacity-building, where the project exceeded its goal for doctoral candidates by supporting 6 PhD and 9 MSc students, directly embedding its knowledge within the next generation of researchers. While these direct engagement and capacity-building activities thrived, the project did not meet the ambitious initial targets for academic publications. This reflects a strategic prioritization of foundational architectural work and early-stage tool development, which naturally require longer timelines for such outputs. Instead, the project focused on producing high-value, consolidated resources like the joint Policy Brief and a comprehensive Outcomes Booklet to ensure its strategic insights reached the broadest possible audience.

The exploitation strategy identified 3 Key Exploitable Results. These KERs are categorized into core technical components, user-facing tools and services (e.g., SplashBoard, BioConnect), and validated pilot use cases in Berlin and Catalonia. The project refined its business models, intellectual property strategies, and sustainability pathways, ensuring the long-term viability and impact of these results through open-source adoption and modular cloud-native architecture. AD4GD's practical advancements in data integration and pilot demonstrations provide a robust foundation for future environmental intelligence and real-world decision-making within the GDDS. AD4GD leaves behind a robust portfolio of openly accessible tools, training materials, visual content, and technical deliverables, exemplified by its Outcomes Booklet and joint Policy Brief. This project offers a roadmap toward an environmental data space that is usable, trusted, and impactful, providing a strong basis for future initiatives.

5.1 STRATEGIC TAKEAWAYS AND LESSONS LEARNT

Prioritize impact channels over volume: For specialized research projects, direct engagement (workshops, stakeholder meetings) and high-impact visual content (videos) proved more effective than pursuing high-volume metrics for generic articles or newsletters.

Create consolidated outputs for broader audiences: Instead of relying solely on individual academic papers, producing collaborative, high-value documents like a joint Policy Brief and a comprehensive Outcomes Booklet was highly effective for disseminating key results and strategic recommendations to a wider audience, including policymakers.

Align KPIs with project maturity and reality: Ambitious KPIs for outputs like academic publications and formal standardization are often unrealistic for foundational projects where results mature late. KPIs should be seen as guiding targets, and final reporting must transparently justify strategic pivots to more effective activities.

A dedicated Task Force is essential for driving exploitation: The success of the exploitation plan depended on a dedicated internal Sustainability Task Force. This provided the necessary governance and accountability to navigate complex decisions on IPR and sustainability, a critical success factor for any multi-partner project.

Adapt to an evolving digital landscape: Communication and dissemination strategies must be agile. The project had to adapt to shifting social media dynamics (pivoting from X/Twitter to LinkedIn) and should have re-evaluated the role of traditional newsletters sooner in a saturated digital environment.

Capacity-Building is a key form of impact: The direct support of students (9 MSc and 6 PhD) and the reuse of project components in follow-up initiatives like the SAGE project are among the most critical and sustainable impacts, ensuring a long-term legacy of knowledge and expertise.

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AD4GD Project Resources & Social Media:

- AD4GD Official Website. (<https://ad4gd.eu/>)
- AD4GD YouTube Channel. (https://www.youtube.com/@ad4gd_project)
- AD4GD Zenodo Community. (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ad4gd/>)
- AD4GD GitHub Repository. (<https://github.com/AD4GD>)
- AD4GD LinkedIn Profile. (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/ad4gd/>)

D7.2 Report on dissemination and exploitation including standardization and communication activities (final)

Co-funded by the European
Union, Switzerland and the
United Kingdom

AD4GD Twitter/X Profile. (https://x.com/ad4gd_project/)

AD4GD Bluesky Profile. (<https://bsky.app/profile/did:plc:ggojwld6t7u5ntni75twwfrf>)

7 ANNEXES

7.1 ANNEX 1: FINAL EVENT SESSIONS SUMMARY

The AD4GD final event co-organized in Vienna with our sister projects under the title “Three Years of Experience Developing the Green Deal Data Space”, hosted a total of 25 sessions including keynote talks, hands-on demonstrations, round tables and a lot of debate. This is a summary of the content of each session:

First Day – 24th June 2025

1. Welcome and Introduction to the Sister Projects – Katharina Schleidt (DataCove, FAIRiCUBE)

Katharina opened the event by explaining the purpose of sharing the lessons learned after three years of work on the Green Deal Data Space. She presented the agenda: a technical day featuring demos and panels, and a strategic policy day. She introduced the four host projects (AD4GD, B-Cubed, USAGE, and FAIRiCUBE), highlighting their approaches and use cases. She concluded with a summary of the common recommendations described in the joint Policy Brief the four projects have presented: data harmonization, semantic enrichment, metadata, data exchange and governance.

2. What REALLY Defines the Green Deal Data Space? – Joan Masó (CREAF, AD4GD)

Joan analysed the main conceptual pillars of the Green Deal Data Space: a heterogeneous data space covering circular economy, biodiversity, pollution, climate change, etc.,. He explained the importance of managing both open and sensitive data, ensuring traceability, quality, authentication, and integrity. He debunked common misconceptions like the GDDS being a big repository, a completely open space without metadata, or a free processing cloud. He also highlighted the two-plane architecture—data plane and control plane—with Eclipse Data Connectors for contracts and data sovereignty.

3. EuroGEO Green Deal Data Space Action Group – Alba Brobia (CREAF, AD4GD)

Alba introduced the EuroGEO Action Group for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS-AG), one of nine action groups within the EuroGEO alliance. The group coordinates research, technical developments and use cases to build a GDDS that is compatible with the GEO work program and the GEOSS infrastructure. Acting as a Community of Practice, the work includes sharing and validating technologies (Data Cubes, OGC APIs, semantic vocabularies, metadata, data connectors), discussing ideas and consolidating viewpoints regarding the GDDS governance and implementation to provide recommendations. She stressed the need for new group members and announced upcoming working sessions, starting from the EuroGEO Workshop 2025 in The Hague in October 2025.

4. Splashboard Graphical User Interface – Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT, AD4GD)

Kristian demonstrated “Splashboard,” an interactive monitoring interface for Berlin’s lakes designed with end users in the context of the AD4GD project. It features an interactive map of Berlin as well as a searchable list of lakes on the landing page, where lake markers are color coded according to the water quality measure “Normalized Difference Trophic Index”. The Detail pages for individual lakes provide map widgets, plots for time-series data (water level, water and air temperature, precipitation and reference-evapotranspiration extracted from a harmonized MinIO bucket), trophic state indices, and ML-based forecasts for high/normal/low precipitation scenarios. Users can filter by date, download data, and mark favourites, aiding local decision-makers.

5. The Green Deal Information Model for Semantic Interoperability – Raul Palma (PSNC, AD4GD)

Raul described AD4GD’s architecture: CSV ingestion, MQTT broker, automated harmonization pipelines (alignment with the SOSA/OM-core model and AD4GD vocabularies), storage in MinIO and a triple store, execution of ML workflows, and automatic publication of SensorThings API via a STA Generation Service. These APIs are then exposed through Eclipse Data Connectors for integration into the data space.

6. The Use of Eclipse Data Connectors in the GDDS – Raul Palma (PSNC, AD4GD)

Raul detailed the minimum components of an Eclipse Data Connector (ECD) implementation (connector, federated catalog, identity hub, contract registry). He showcased two dashboards (provider and consumer) where assets, policies, and contract definitions are defined, and data negotiation and transfer take place. Using a sample observation series, he demonstrated how a consumer discovers an asset in the catalog, negotiates the contract, and downloads data via the connector.

7. TAPIS: Connecting to Data in the Data Space – Joan Masó (CREAF, AD4GD)

Joan explained TAPIS ("Tables from APIs"), a tool for transforming SensorThings API responses into tables. He demonstrated how TAPIS is able to extract the list of resources in the GDDS by connecting to the federated catalog, select one, negotiate the contract until it gets the download URL and extracts the data. TAPIS hides the underlying complexity, displays data in tabular format, and services in an adapted way.

8. Creating a Data Space for Cities Using Open Source Software – Jeroen Ticheler (GeoCat, USAGE)

Jeroen presented USAGE's open source stack, built on GeoNetwork, GeoServer, QGIS, AngularJS, OGC API-Features, DCAT-AP, and INSPIRE profiles. He highlighted the evolution toward a microservices architecture and specialized apps (search, editor, SSO with Keycloak, catalog APIs, automatic conversion of ISO/OGC/DCAT metadata), and showcased the city catalog with a "Netflix-style" UI for data/tool/algorithms browsing experience and fully functional metadata support for algorithm & tools.

9. FACTS: Alternative for Trusted and Sensitive Assets Exchange – Andreas Matheus (Secure Dimensions)

Andreas introduced FACTS, a blockchain-based approach for an immutable catalog containing asset metadata and hashes, edge-less certification with zero-knowledge proofs and selective disclosure, and issuer, holder, and verifier roles. He illustrated the workflow: discovering an asset in the catalog, issuing a certificate to the user, and verification by a trusted service before accessing or processing sensitive data, ensuring privacy and sovereignty without duplicating data.

10. Bioconnect Graphical User Interface – Kristian Berwanger (Fraunhofer FIT, AD4GD)

Kristian showcased "Bioconnect," an interface for the habitat connectivity pilot of the AD4GD project. In this GUI, users are provided with a map based view of Catalonia presenting land usage information as well as different bioconnectivity indices, species occurrences and other spatial layers. Furthermore, users can create their own scenarios based on land usage changes and investigate implications on different bioconnectivity indices. Calculated scenarios can be downloaded or saved for later review and comparison. Thus the tool improves large-data accessibility for biodiversity research.

11. I-ADOPT Ontology Framework for Environmental Variables – Barbara Magagna (GO FAIR Foundation)

Barbara presented I-ADOPT, a FAIR ontology framework developed between 2019–2021 for harmonizing observable property vocabularies without changing existing terms. It provides qualified references and machine-readable descriptions to map across standards. I-ADOPT supports interoperability for observations, measurements, simulations, and aggregations, offering guidelines to document variable semantics consistently.

12. Expert Panel: Lessons Learned from the Projects – Chair & Panelists.

Representatives from AD4GD, FAIRiCUBE, USAGE, and B-Cubed discussed key takeaways: clarify data space concepts for non-IT stakeholders, balance technology push with stakeholder needs, ensure resource estimation for AI/ML workflows, and apply metadata/certification to ML models for trust. Panelists emphasized human-in-the-loop for metadata and the evolving role of standards.

13. Expert Panel: Common Recommendations for the Green Deal Data Space – Chair & Panelists.

Panelists reviewed five policy recommendations from the joint brief: 1) Data harmonization; 2) Semantic enrichment; 3) Metadata; 4) Data Exchange; 5) Sustainable governance and stakeholder engagement. Speakers included Katharina Schleidt (DataCove, FAIRiCUBE), Raul Palma (PSNC, AD4GD), Fabio Vinci (Epsilon Italia, USAGE), Andreas Matheus (Secure Dimensions, AD4GD), and Joan Masó (CREAF, AD4GD).

They highlighted advancing INSPIRE models and metadata provision. Panelists also emphasized the importance of ensuring interoperability and trust in data processing and exchange mechanisms.

14. Data Harmonisation in FAIRiCUBE – Maria Ricci (space4environment, FAIRiCUBE)

Maria Ricci detailed FAIRiCUBE's data harmonization process: ingesting heterogeneous EO and in-situ datasets, mapping to a reference grid, transforming to cloud-optimized NetCDF, populating metadata fields, and publishing via OGC and SensorThings APIs. She shared challenges in undocumented formats, manual curation, and the need for pipelines that ensure analysis-ready, interoperable data cubes.

15. Biodiversity Data Cubes – Lina M. Estupinan-Suarez (iDiv, B-Cubed)

Lina Estupinan presented results from the work on Biodiversity Data Cubes carried out in the B-Cubed project. She focused on strategies to enhance the implementation of FAIR principles when working with biodiversity data cubes. She first demonstrated a new feature on the GBIF website that enables users to create species occurrence cubes, with the corresponding SQL code provided for further customisation. Additionally, she introduced the EBV Data Portal as a platform that supports users in searching, exploring, downloading, and visualising geospatial biodiversity datasets. The security implications of offering an open SQL service versus parameterised server-side queries were noted.

16. How to use EO data to uncover evolutionary patterns in fruit flies– Susanna Ioni (NHMV, FAIRiCUBE)

Sonja Steidl presented FAIRiCUBE Use Case 3, which explores how Earth Observation (EO) data can help study evolutionary patterns in *Drosophila melanogaster*, a fruit fly species that has globally adapted alongside humans. By combining genetic data from over 400 European populations with EO variables (e.g. climate, pesticides), the team aimed to understand how the environment influences genetic variation. To support this, they developed a tool that extracts relevant EO data (via Rasdaman) based on the sample's location and date. Using multivariate statistics like Redundancy Analysis, they found links between certain genetic markers and environmental factors such as pesticide use. The approach, though focused on fruit flies, is applicable to other species and helps biologists integrate EO data without needing deep technical expertise.

17. DATA4LAND: How to Enrich Land Use Land Cover Datasets? – Vitalii Kriukov (Aston University, AD4GD)

Vitalii outlined a multi-level enrichment pipeline for land use/land cover data: ingesting regional LULC categories; retrieving retrospective OpenStreetMap data acting as ecological barriers (such as roads, railways, and waterways), preprocessing, and integrating auxiliary datasets and expert knowledge to support dynamic ecological connectivity metrics (e.g., carbon stock assessments). He discussed performance considerations for large areas, scalability across AD4GD case studies and the need for domain-specific customisation.

18. Water Quality and Availability Indices for Small Urban Lakes – Malte Zamzow (KWB, AD4GD)

Malte showcased the results from the water pilot of the AD4GD project in Berlin. There are over 400 small urban lakes in Berlin, which are ecologically important but largely unregulated and understudied. The pilot aimed to enhance existing data, create new data, and integrate both for better decision-making. They developed a satellite-based Trophic Index using Sentinel-2 imagery to estimate water quality, validated, and applied to track trends. They also adapted the CrowdWater app for citizen science, generating indicators based on simple user observations. All data can be fed into a central dashboard, enabling efficient lake monitoring.

19. Compliant collection, processing & display of heterogeneous data George Salukvadze (IoT Lab, AD4GD)

George Salukvadze (IoT Lab) presented a prototype from the IoT Lab called the Universal Device Gateway, aimed at integrating heterogeneous data sources into a single, human-readable user-friendly interface. Demonstrated using Berlin's urban lakes, the system combines real-time sensor data—like water levels from SensorThings-based APIs—with additional datasets such as air quality sensors, Sentinel-2 satellite imagery,

and population data from Eurostat as well as data regarding Data Processing using DP-ID service. Though still a prototype, it demonstrates the feasibility of creating a comprehensive and privacy-aware data integration platform for IoT data.

Second Day – 25th June 2025

20. Where do we stand with dataspace in Europe? – Christoph Mertens (IDSA)

Christoph Mertens (IDSA) presented the state of data spaces in Europe, focusing on the evolution from technical architectures to scalable, value-driven ecosystems. He emphasized the importance of trust, standardization (especially via the Dataspace Protocol), and data policy enforcement. Highlighted the shortage of high-quality training data for AI and how regulated company data within data spaces could be part of the solution. He underscored interoperability across four levels (technical, semantic, organizational, legal) and called for international cooperation. The IDSA now supports over 180 members across 31 countries and is pursuing ISO standardization for the dataspace protocol.

21. Sibling Projects Outcomes and GDDS Demonstration – Katharina Schleidt & Raul Palma

This session aimed to demonstrate how the sister projects were able to build a simple working version of the Green Deal Data Space integrating diverse data from the four projects. Katharina Schleidt (DataCove, FAIRiCUBE) recounted how sibling projects were rapidly adapting existing services to integrate their datasets with the GDDS via Eclipse Dataspace Connectors, following AD4GD's approach. Raul Palma showcased the current state of deployment: five participants now have connectors, and metadata and assets are becoming discoverable and negotiable. Raul explained the architecture, minimum setup, configuration steps, and how assets and metadata from GeoNetwork are made visible and accessible for negotiation and transfer within the dataspace.

22. Outcomes from B-Cubed and the GDDS – Quentin Groom (Meise Botanic Garden)

Quentin Groom (Meise Botanic Garden, B-Cubed) explained B-Cubed's mission to transform raw, heterogeneous biodiversity data into usable biodiversity datacubes. He presented GBIF as a mature, federated biodiversity infrastructure that works as a data space, even if it doesn't identify as such. GBIF's open standards, licenses, and identifiers enable FAIR and reproducible data sharing. B-Cubed adds value by generating taxon-time-space occurrence cubes, using API-based and downloadable access, facilitating environmental integration. Emphasis was placed on openness, reproducibility, and governance, with a caution against closing biodiversity datasets unnecessarily.

23. The Future of the Green Deal Data Space: Insights from the SAGE Project – Mark Dietrich (Bloodstone Consulting, SAGE)

Mark introduced SAGE as a large-scale Green Deal Data Space project focused on 10 diverse use cases. He laid out functional requirements for future data spaces: enabling data sovereignty, trust, policy enforcement, semantic and legal interoperability, and secure processing environments. Mark emphasized that data spaces are not storage or processing platforms but must support metadata-rich discovery and federated governance. He proposed mapping and crosswalking between domain ontologies rather than enforcing a single model and encouraged bridging silos among research infrastructures, digital twins, and policy domains.

24. The Present and Future of the GDDS: FACTS – Andreas Matheus (Secure Dimensions)

Andreas presented "FACTS" as a connector-less alternative for data exchange in the GDDS. He argued that sometimes complex EDC infrastructure is unnecessary—what matters most is verifiability and authenticity. FACTS uses verifiable credentials and decentralized identifiers to assure data provenance. It shifts focus from data control to certifying authenticity and integrity through cryptographic proof, supporting a lightweight and sovereign approach to sharing open environmental datasets.

25. Policy Brief Launch - Unlocking the Full Potential of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS)

The four sibling projects have collaborated to produce a concise Policy Brief focused on five pillars critical to the success of the Green Deal Data Space: data harmonization, semantic interoperability, metadata management, data exchange, and governance. Together they presented these recommendations in the form of a policy brief openly available on Zenodo. After the presentation of the recommendations, representatives from all projects discussed their view on the main points advocated in the brief.